

eMOTIONAL Cities

Mapping the cities through the senses
of those who make them

DELIVERABLE 5.4

Report on the results of the outdoor experiments

FEBRUARY 2025

Project Title	eMotional Cities
Deliverable	Deliverable 5.4. – Report on the results of the outdoor experiments
Work package	WP5
Task	T5.6 & T5.7
Number of pages	147
Dissemination level	Public
Leader	FMUL
Contributors	IGOT, DTU, SLAB, CLIMA, MSU
Peer-reviewers	Paulo Morgado (IGOT)
Date	21 February 2025
File name	eMCities_WP5_D5.4_v1
Version	V1
Main authors	<p>Coordination: Bruno Miranda (FMUL)</p> <p>Contributions:</p> <p>Marta Conceição (FMUL-exp3); João Amaro (FMUL-exp4); Ana Bonifácio (FMUL-exp4 & 5); Pedro Rocha (FMUL-exp5); Inês Ramos (FMUL-exp5).</p> <p>André Leite Rodrigues (IGOT-exp3); Rafael Ramusga (IGOT-exp4); Paulo Morgado (IGOT-exp3, 4 and 5).</p> <p>Carlos Azevedo (DTU-exp3 & 4), Bastián Henriquez-Jara, Sonja Haustein and Mafalda Pires (DTU-exp3).</p> <p>Ángel Blanco (SLAB-exp4 & 5); Claire Braboszcz (SLAB-exp5); Eleni Kroupi (SLAB-exp4); Aureli Soria-Frisch (SLAB-exp4 & 5).</p> <p>Ata Chokhachian (CLIMA-exp4).</p> <p>Zeenat Kotval-Karamchandani (MSU-exp4); Tyson Burghardt (MSU-exp5).</p> <p>Gonçalo Lopes (NGR-exp4 & 5); André Almeida (NGR-exp4 & 5); João Frazão (NGR-exp4 & 5).</p>

Disclaimer: The analysis and maps presented in these reports should not be subject to extrapolation that leads to direct causation in analysis and conclusions as it can produce unintended consequences.

Index

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
1.1 Neuroscience experiments of WP5: a brief summary	8
1.2 Report structure	10
2. Findings from “Experiment 3: Mobile sensing of stress and emotional effects of daily urban experience”	13
2.1 Experimental framework	14
2.2 Field deployment	16
2.3 Data analysis and post-processing	16
2.4 Early Insights	21
2.5 Results from the acute stress and decision-making task	28
2.6 Ongoing and future analyses	32
3. Findings from “Experiment 4: Outdoor neuroscience experiments”	33
3.1 Experiment protocol synthesis	35
3.2 Lisbon case-study	36
3.3 Outdoor neuroscience experiments: results from each path	43
4. Neural effects of naturalness and crowding from outdoor experiments	92
5. Findings from “Experiment 5: Clinical experiment”	100
5.1 Experimental protocol	101
5.2 Behavioural results	120
5.3 EEG results – EmoWave® feature analysis	134
5.4 Other ongoing studies for complementary brain and body physiological responses across the VR scenarios	137
6. Conclusions	144
7. References	146

Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D5.4: Report on the results of the outdoor experiments” that belongs to the “WP5 - Neuroscience experiments” of the European project “eMOTIONAL Cities - Mapping the cities through the senses of those who make them” (Project Number 945307; Project Acronym eMOTIONAL Cities).

This technical report aims to document the findings obtained throughout the outdoor neuroscience experiments, as well as the clinical experiment. It reflects the work primarily performed in tasks “T5.6 – Outdoor experiments: procedures and data collection” and “T5.7 – Clinical population study: recruitment and data collection”. Moreover, it reflects some of the protocol procedures defined in “D5.1” applied to specific locations of the case-study cities – or “hot spots”, derived in WP4 (D4.3).

The described results refer to findings from:

- “Experiment 3: Mobile sensing of stress and emotional effects of daily urban experience”: where participants, recruited in Copenhagen and Lisbon, used a dedicated smartphone application and wearable sensors (including wristbands to capture physiological markers) during their daily routines. The collected data, combined with machine learning analyses revealed significant correlations between mobility patterns, self-reported emotional states, and physiological stress markers. These insights highlight how everyday travel and activities modulate emotional responses in urban environments.
- “Experiment 4: Outdoor neuroscience experiments”: involving real-life walks wearing several types of environmental (for noise, air pollution, microclimate), neurological (EEG), and physiological (galvanic skin response and heart rate) sensors. The results underscored how different urban typologies – characterized by elements such as natural green spaces versus densely built areas, affect neural markers related to cognitive load and emotional states. For instance, natural settings tended to elicit more positive emotional engagement and lower stress responses compared to crowded, traffic-intensive zones.
- “Experiment 5: Clinical experiment”: reports on a case-control study comparing the spatial navigation performance of elderly subjects with mild cognitive impairment against healthy controls using a virtual reality task. The clinical experiment tested the hypothesis that redesigning urban environments according to dementia-inclusive guidelines can enhance navigational performance and cognitive function. The obtained evidence indicates that VR-based interventions might improve spatial orientation by mitigating cognitive deficits, while also suggesting that different wayfinding strategies are influenced by urban design.

Overall, this report demonstrates the potential of an interdisciplinary approach – merging neuroscience, urban research, and advanced portable sensor technology – to shape the future of urban health planning. This novel integration of methodologies not only contributes to academic knowledge but also provides actionable insights for policymakers tasked with designing urban spaces that promote both cognitive and emotional well-being. Furthermore, it also provides the required substrates for evidence-based knowledge generation (in WP6) and scenario discovery case-specifications (in WP7).

1. Introduction

The eMOTIONAL Cities is a “Research and Innovation Action” (RIA) that investigates how natural and built urban environments shape the neurobiology underlying human cognitive and emotional processing. The main goal of the eMOTIONAL Cities “WP5—Neuroscience experiments” work package is to provide neural evidence of brain representations for decision-making and emotional behaviour elicited by the urban environment.

The work presented in this document aims to address the following objective of WP5:

- “O5.4 - Perform urban outdoor experiments and collect brain signals with wearable EEG, eye-tracking data, and other relevant physiological signals: this will complement the VR/AR experiments by extending face-validity. We will develop an outdoor field experiment to relate participants’ cognitive and emotional processing to place. Participants will wear eye-tracking glasses, wearable EEG, and environmental and physiological sensors”.

As planned in the work plan of T5.6, we have collected environmental and individual data from healthy volunteers (including the young and the elderly; and gender-balanced) while they performed specific urban trajectories (as identified in T4.2) across our case-study cities. As explained in previous technical reports of the project, the required technological developments (of the wearable kit) and protocol improvements (due to data collection difficulties encountered) have made the comparative analysis across sites hard (because, for example, data from London was collected mostly for benchmarking and during optimisation of the wearable data collection kit; significant EEG artifacts were encountered in Lansing due to overhead electricity networks, etc). Hence, the decision here was to focus on the more robust datasets so that this report could be helpful (and with an adequate comprehensive depth). Furthermore, the idea was also to extend analysis or perspectives presented in previous deliverables (e.g., to provide follow-up of the stakeholders workshop described in D5.3; and the [technical reports](#), for mapping hotspots, from the [D4.3](#)).

- “O5.5 - Identify if vulnerable groups and gender-related aspects are relevant for urban health design or interventions: this will be conducted across the indoor/outdoor experiments and by focusing on urban features eliciting gender-related and vulnerable group (particularly, elderly people) differences in cognitive and emotional processing (e.g., factors related to safety/risk perception). By adopting a mixed methodology this will ensure that robust evidence is obtained to raise awareness and inform policy making for a more inclusive urban design”.

The objective was successfully achieved by integrating our real-world outdoor experiments (exp. 3 and 4) and controlled clinical studies (exp. 5) to investigate the influence of gender-related and vulnerable group factors on urban health and design. By conducting field studies in diverse urban environments, we systematically examined age-related and gender-based differences in cognitive and emotional processing of urban spaces, with a particular focus on environmental stressors. The study design ensured a gender-balanced representation and included participants across various age groups, enabling robust comparative analyses of urban features that differentially impact men, women, and elderly individuals. To further explore vulnerable populations, a clinical study involving mild cognitive impairment (MCI) patients was conducted to assess how urban interventions could enhance their spatial orientation and wayfinding. The self-reported (and other qualitative interviews) and objectively measured (through neuroimaging and sensors for physiological signals) outcomes provided empirical evidence on the cognitive and perceptual challenges faced by vulnerable groups, highlighting the need for inclusive and “neuro-informed” urban design strategies. These results contribute to evidence-based policymaking, reinforcing the importance of designing public spaces that enhance navigability and overall well-being for all demographic groups, particularly those at higher risk of environmental stressors and spatial disorientation in cities.

- “O5.6 - Conduct a clinical study in patients with mild cognitive impairment to obtain evidence that urban planning and design can have an impact on this vulnerable group: as little is known about how the urban environment impacts cognitive dysfunction, a clinical study will compare a vulnerable group – elderly patients at increased risk of developing dementia – to healthy controls. We will test the hypothesis that performance on a VR/AR spatial navigation task could be improved by re-designing the outdoor neighbourhood”.

We present interesting results obtained from the small-scale, multicentre (at FMUL – coordinating centre, and at MSU), exploratory, gender-balanced, analytical, and case-control study, where the spatial navigation performance of elderly subjects with mild cognitive impairment are compared between a virtual reality scenario with and without dementia-inclusive urban planning and design principles. Data from brain activity is also presented to further explore causal relationships of these human-environment interaction effects.

1.1 Neuroscience experiments of WP5: a brief summary

As mentioned before (in [D5.1](#) and [D5.3](#)), the eMOTIONAL Cities have contemplated a total of five experiments for the WP5 activities (**Figure 1.1**).

Figure 1.1. The different types of experimental settings – indoor, outdoor and clinical, as well as the various approaches and techniques used for the five eMOTIONAL Cities experiments.

Here, we provide a summary of the *outdoor* and *clinical* experiments that we consider relevant for a better understanding of this report (see [D5.3](#) for the results of the indoor experiments).

- **Experiment 3 - Mobile sensing of stress and emotional effects of daily urban experience** (also abbreviated as the *app* or *mobility app experiment*): in this *outdoor* experiment, participants were asked to use, during two weeks their smartphone with an Application – a mobility app, specifically designed for performing a customised adaptive stated perception surveys regarding context-specific built and travel environment. Moreover, while collecting app data on daily travel and activities (and on self-reported emotional states), participants have also worn a wristband to collect stress-related physiological signals across multiple days (and used in the modelling of the travel behaviour). Both the mobility app and the use of the physiological sensors were applied in [Copenhagen](#) and [Lisbon](#) case-study cities. However, the Lisbon participants have also been invited to come to FMUL fMRI facilities (after finishing the data collection for the app) to perform a decision-making task under acute stress while brain and physiological data were collected. The main goal was to

establish correlations between daily activity/mobility patterns with stress signals (a more chronic type of stress related to the daily routine patterns of the two weeks of app data collection as well as some acutely induced stress) on cognitive and decision-making planning. Here in this report, we will be presenting outcomes obtained in Copenhagen from the mobility app survey (as for this city the analytical work was in a more advanced stage and to avoid a very extensive report); together with the behavioural results derived in Lisbon from the acute stress and decision-making task.

- **Experiment 4 - Outdoor neuroscience experiments** (also abbreviated as the *walk* or *outdoor experiment*): in this *outdoor* experiment, volunteers (gender-balanced and including young and some older participants) performed a particular urban path wearing a portable kit with several types of environmental (for climate and thermal comfort data), behavioural (eye tracking), neurological (EEG) and physiological (heart rate and galvanic skin response) sensors. The aim was to investigate in real-life scenarios relationships between multiple urban environments and individual impact signals. Furthermore, this experiment was critical to evaluate the benefits and limitations of running experiments in more naturalistic scenarios (see similarities between the EEG responses of the indoor experiment 2 in [D5.3](#) and the EEG results presented here for this outdoor experiment). Here in this report, we will present data collected from the outdoor experiments in Lisbon (data collected for the other cities are available on the dashboard of D6.5).
- **Experiment 5 - Clinical experiment** (also abbreviated as the *virtual reality*, *clinical*, or *MCI experiment*): this *clinical* experiment will consist of a small-scale, two-center (FMUL and MSU), exploratory, gender-balanced, analytical, and case-control study, where the performance of twenty-five elderly subjects with MCI on a virtual spatial navigation task will be compared to a similar age- and education-matched group of controls. The task will involve both current and virtually modified (and optimised as a function of some dementia-based design guiding principles) urban space environments (consisting of a virtual reconstruction of a real neighbourhood of Lisbon). The behavioural performance (more specifically the amount of navigational errors) of the two groups following the specific modifications (or virtual city improvements) will be compared (together with some additional comparative differences at the level of EEG brain activity as well). Here in this report, we will present data from patients recruited in both Lisbon (FMUL) and Michigan (MSU) sites.

1.2 Report structure

After this introductory part, the report is structured in three sections describing technical details and results of the conducted outdoor neuroscience experiments. Each section also includes specific subsections that detail relevant information applied to that specific work (including methodology, results, and discussion). Here, we provide a summary of each section to better support and guide the reader.

As part of the procedures and findings from the outdoor “Experiment 3: Mobile sensing of stress and emotional effects of daily urban experience”, we have six sub-sections:

- “Experimental framework”: in this section, we provide a short description of how the experiment was conceived to assess daily experiences and environmental influence on emotional and physiological states. It involves details on participants’ recruitment, integration of the mobility survey smartphone application, and the use of the wearable device for emotional physiological markers, and the post-experiment evaluation (similar information is also available on our [website](#)).
- “Field deployment”: provides a short description, for both Copenhagen and Lisbon, about the number of participants, and their characteristics; as well as details regarding the pre- and post-surveys, user-validated app data, and physiological measurements.
- “Data analysis and post-processing”: this part provides a brief introduction to how the collected physiological signals were used by a machine-learning model to compute stress and emotional responses daily (see [Dubois et al., 2023](#) for further technical details); and also how mobility patterns were derived from the mobility survey data.
- “Early insights”: reports on the results linking the ML-generated emotional or physiological responses with the computed activity patterns (for a single participant across the day; and for the overall activity types across all participants); and also describes spatial analysis outcomes from the pedestrian journeys.
- “Results from the acute stress and decision-making task”: this section provides the behavioural results obtained in Lisbon for the performance of participants on the decision-making task under acute stress.
- “Ongoing and future analyses“: describe the current activities being developed by the research teams to further exploit the collected data.

Similarly, as part of the procedures and findings from “Experiment 4: Outdoor Neuroscience experiments” we have four sub-sections:

- “Experimental protocol synthesis”: this section describes how participants were recruited, their baseline assessments (before running the experiment), and details on how researchers prepared the equipment and briefed participants before the guided city walk and the procedures at the end (feedback on their perceptions and emotions).
- “Lisbon-case study”: it involves the details on the selection and characterisation of Lisbon paths – more specifically how public spaces were classified into different typologies; moreover, it also explains how environmental measures were calculated, the metrics used for individual body physiological responses and the way brain activity measured with EEG was used to map emotional and cognitive states.
- “Outdoor neuroscience experiments: results from each path”: here, the outcomes contemplating the environmental features (noise levels, air pollution, and thermal comfort), body physiological responses (galvanic skin response and heart rate), and brain activity in EEG are systematically mapped for each of the six main paths of Lisbon.
- “Neural effects of naturalness and crowding from outdoor experiments”: this part of the results focuses on a broader evaluation of urban environments by investigating the relationship between EEG responses and two key perceptual dimensions of a city walk experience: naturalness (the extent to which a space is perceived as green or natural) and crowding (the subjective sense of population density and spatial confinement). These perceptual dimensions are crucial, as they influence cognitive and emotional states, potentially modulating stress levels, cognitive load, and overall well-being.

For “Experiment 5: clinical experiment” we have four sub-sections that cover protocol and results:

- “Experimental protocol”: this part provides the published protocol manuscript describing our task design and methodological approach to compare the navigation performance of both subject groups – healthy controls and those with mild cognitive impairment; furthermore, the characterisation of the VR urban spaces created (control scenario and the optimised one) are also provided.
- “Behavioural results”: here the results from the VR navigation task are shown and differences in wayfinding performance are depicted between patients and controls

and across the two tested scenarios. Data reveal distinct patterns of navigation errors, with patients generally exhibiting higher error rates than controls. The findings provide robust evidence on how urban design and planning could have a significant cognitive impact on a vulnerable and diseased group of individuals.

- “EEG results - EmoWave feature analysis”: this part of the results refers to the findings obtained from an EEG algorithm developed by STARLAB partner that extracted various features (valence, arousal, engagement, attention, and fatigue) while participants conducted the navigation experiment.
- “Other ongoing studies for complementary brain and body physiological responses across the VR scenarios”: this involves the description of additional studies (i.e., going beyond the initial goals of the project) being conducted by the researchers to potentiate more outcomes from the virtually created urban environments (e.g., experiments where VR-headsets are used by stakeholders or citizen promoting their engagement by allowing them to "walk through" proposed developments, providing valuable feedback on aesthetics, accessibility, and functionality).

Finally, a conclusion section will provide a short summary of the work developed and will relate to the previous WP4 activities and subsequent use in the WP6 and WP7 deliverables.

2. Findings from “Experiment 3: Mobile sensing of stress and emotional effects of daily urban experience”

The increase of the urban population to half of the world’s population led to urban densification and a shrink of green areas, which positively affect city dwellers’ well-being and health (Bratman, 2019), especially mental health (Tost, 2019), and help to recover from intense stress periods (Berry, 2007). Policymakers often neglect the urban environment’s effects on well-being and health due to a lack of knowledge and evidence on the complex relationship between individual travel decision-making and emotional states.

Much effort has been made to detect individuals’ stress levels in controlled experiments. Nonetheless, these insulate individuals from the plethora of stimuli that affect their emotions and make it difficult to observe individuals’ stress levels for extended periods. Thus, observing individuals during more extended periods in their daily-life activity can reveal both the short (Castro, 2020) and prolonged (Smets, 2018) exposure to different built environments on emotional states. In addition, following the geographic location of the individuals over time while performing daily activities and travels would help to evaluate the impact of these on their well-being and to identify stressful urban areas.

Studies considering smartphone-based solutions to capture fluctuations in emotional state and well-being (through multiple assessments per day and across various contexts) have been increasing in the last few years, but few have focused on the relationship between real-life stress, mobility patterns, and decision-making. In particular, to the best of our knowledge, no studies on this relationship have been published that provide an estimate of stress from actual physiological data, rather than self-reported data collected through validated psychological scales. This field study aims to bridge this gap.

This study was designed to collect new and unique data leveraging new mobile sensing devices and wearable (bio)sensing technologies for understanding the dynamics between emotional states and travel decision-making, in two different case study cities (Copenhagen and Lisbon). From a neuroscience perspective, a lab-based experiment was also conducted at the end of the outdoor data collection (specifically in Lisbon), allowing us to explore how the real-life (outdoor) stress and decision-making results reflect on those from a well-established planning task, under controlled settings.

2.1 Experimental framework

We propose eMOTIONAL Daily Patterns, an experimental framework using a wearable device and a smartphone framework to collect detailed data on self-reported emotions, psychophysiological markers, activities, travel, and related contextual information on their daily lives. The framework includes three stages described below (**Figure 2.1**).

Figure 2.1. Diagram illustrating the eMOTIONAL Daily Patterns' Data collection framework.

2.1.1. Screening and Pre-Survey

In the *screening survey*, we ensured that the participants were suitable for the study (checking for relevant health conditions and smartphone availability) and balanced the diversity of the sample by collecting and monitoring information on gender, age, residential area, and primary occupation. The *pre-survey* was web-based and allowed for the collection of relevant factors that may influence emotions beyond demographics, namely: (1) habits, such as regular physical activity and coffee, alcohol, and tobacco intake; (2) attitudes toward transport modes, and mobility; (3) environmental mastery, as one aspect of psychological well-being particularly related to stress; (4) personality factors, namely the "honesty-humility" domain and the facets "prudence", and "anxiety" of the HEXACO inventory; (5) mild cognitive impairment using questions from the P-AD8 questionnaire; (6) mental state from a validated self-report scale on depression, anxiety, and stress (DASS-21); and (7) other relevant questions on the participant's height, weight, and medication intake (that may affect the physiological measurements) and on their perceived problems related to their physical health.

2.1.2. Naturalistic Experiment

The Empatica E4 medical wristband and a personalized version of the mobile sensing app X-ing were used for data collection. The former is a wearable device that records physiological signals including the blood volume pulse (BVP) – from which heart rate and heart rate variability can be computed –, electrodermal activity (EDA; or galvanic skin response, GSR) used to infer arousal and stress levels, and skin temperature (SKT). As for the *X-ing mobile app*, it logs space-time trajectories, infers transportation modes, and categorizes stops as activities (home, work, shopping, social, etc.), allowing the participant to review, validate, and provide additional information on the trip's or activity's attributes (travel party, when the activity was planned, etc.). We extended the App capabilities by sampling subjective emotional states using the Short Mood Scale (Wilhelm & Schoebi, 2007) as a random Ecological Momentary Assessment (EMA) and (end-of-day) Ecological Retrospective Assessment (ERA). EMAs and ERAs were paired with questions on the impact of surrounding environments or other emotional stimuli. Moreover, a daily self-perceived sleep quality question (adapted from the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index – PSQI) was obtained by the app. Simultaneously, the Empatica E4 continuously gathers physiological metrics during wakefulness.

2.1.3. Post-Survey and Choice Experiment

The *post-survey* collected feedback on the study protocol and assessed the impact of major events on participants' stress levels during the previous naturalistic experiment stage. A set of standard questions on other factors with potential impact on the overall emotional state of the participants was also performed, namely a rapid screening of the restless legs syndrome and a set of questions on the use of social media. Finally, and only in Lisbon, a classical psychological experiment was performed along with an fMRI (functional magnetic resonance imaging) protocol. Here, participants performed a standard two-stage Markov decision-making task (from the field of contemporary reinforcement learning (RL) and decision-making theories; task adapted from Daw et al., 2011), which is commonly used in the neuroscience domain to differentiate human decision-making approaches – for a choice behaviour either more goal-directed (or model-based decisions) or habitual (model-free decisions). Inferring on how each individual resorts to these two processes helps understand immediate rewards accounting and longer-term goals, which has implications in various human behavioral contexts, from habits to learning and adaptability in future behavioural nudging.

2.2 Field deployment

2.2.1 Copenhagen

We deployed the eMOTIONAL Daily Patterns framework in a trial in the greater Copenhagen area (GCPH), Denmark. It included 119 participants (53 men, 65 women, and one nondisclosed), with an average age of 49.9 ± 16.9 years, recruited through a representative panel of the GCPH. Participants received a gift card compensation. The experiment included in-person single Pre- and Post-Survey sessions and an observed average of 13.2 ± 2.4 days of user-validated app data and 12.1 ± 2.9 daily hours of physiological measurements. The data collection spanned from November 2023 to July 2024 due to the limited number of wristbands available.

2.2.2 Lisbon

In the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, a total of 86 participants completed the field experiment (outdoor and indoor). This sample consisted of 35 men (41%) and 51 women (59%), with an average age of 32.7 ± 10.3 years. The experiment included in-person single Pre- and Post-Survey sessions (the latter taking place at the lab, at the start of the indoor experiment) and it consisted of at least 10 days of data collection – both user-validated app data and physiological measurements – from August 2024 to December 2024. Participants received a gift card compensation of (~75€) after concluding both the outdoor and indoor experiments.

2.3 Data analysis and post-processing

2.3.1 Physiological signals

As previously introduced, we used a modern wearable wristband (the Empatica E4 [1]) to record physiological signals in a non-intrusive way, including blood volume pulse (BVP; sampled at 64Hz), electrodermal activity (EDA; sampled at 4Hz) and skin temperature (TEMP; sampled at 4Hz).

Based on Russel's circumplex model of affect, an emotion can be characterized in a continuous 2-dimensional space built on two axes: *valence* – which indicates user's positive or negative (i.e., quality of) affect; and *arousal* – which measures how passive/calm or active/excited a user is (i.e., the intensity of the emotional state). Emotion recognition from physiological signals is usually achieved using supervised machine learning algorithms that require ground truth labels for training. However,

collecting fine-grained labels, as opposed to single post-stimuli emotion labels, is costly and time-consuming. This is particularly unfeasible in real-life longitudinal settings, as it increases the risk of dropout and disengagement.

Taking this into account, in this work we opted for two different yet complementary approaches. On one hand, we computed commonly used indicators of stress based on physiological signals, such as heart rate and heart rate variability (from BVP), amplitude, number of peaks, rise, and recovery times (from EDA), and skin temperature central tendency and dispersion indicators (from TEMP), as introduced in previous reports. On the other hand, we also explored the results of a deep-seeded clustering model for emotion detection developed by our team (Dubois et al., 2023), which allows us to infer emotions from physiological measurements with minimal supervision (i.e., with labels). The architecture of the model is presented in **Figure 2.2**.

Figure 2.2. Diagram illustrating the semi-supervised model for emotion recognition (from Dubois et al., 2023).

The model combines an autoencoder for unsupervised feature representation, with k-means clustering for fine-grained classification. It automatically extracts features from the recorded physiological signals to form consistent clusters (in an unsupervised manner), while its output, i.e., the cluster membership, represents the degree to which each time window matches a specific emotion. Thus, it allows for fine-grained emotion detection based on broader retrospective assessments, and, due to the unsupervised nature of the autoencoder, its application does not require domain knowledge.

So far, the model has been applied to two different (publicly available) indoor datasets, namely WESAD (Schmidt et al., 2018) and Stress-Predict (Iqbal et al., 2022), showing reasonable to good performance, reaching 79% accuracy on WESAD and 60% on

Stress-Predict. A proof-of-concept example for this field study also shows that the model can learn to recognize the four quadrants of the circumplex model of affect, across daily activities and trips, in outdoor (real-life) settings - however, this result must be interpreted with caution as it refers to a single session of a single participant.

2.3.2. Mobility patterns

The study of mobility and activity patterns has been a key focus of research in recent years. Much of this work aims to identify traveler profiles and the purposes behind their trips, to better quantify mobility impacts (Alho et al., 2022). A large body of such research focuses on individuals' daily activities, using data from travel-activity diaries collected via smartphone applications (Tajaddini et al., 2020). This research helps uncover traveler behaviors and mobility trends, contributing to more efficient urban transport planning.

Aligned with this mobility-related research, we identify mobility profiles from the complex sequence of trips and activities collected in this experiment using clustering techniques. Clustering these sequences requires measuring the differences or distances between them. However, assessing sequence similarity is challenging, as activities and travel and activity patterns are often interdependent. Small variations in sequences can significantly increase the measured distance when using traditional metrics like Euclidean or Hamming distance. The Hamming distance is defined as:

$$d_H(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^n 1(x_i \neq y_i)$$

Where:

- $d_H(x, y)$ is the Hamming distance between sequences x and y .
- n is the length of the sequences.
- x_i and y_i are the elements at position i in sequences x and y , respectively.
- $1(x_i \neq y_i)$ is an indicator function that equals 1 if $x_i \neq y_i$, and 0 otherwise.

The Hamming distance assigns a constant exchange cost, regardless of activity type. This limitation can make it ineffective in distinguishing between slightly different and significantly different observations, leading to potential misclassifications. To overcome this issue, we introduced a distance matrix \mathbf{D} , which D_{ij} represents the numerical distance or exchange cost between travel/activity i and travel/activity j , being 0 if $i=j$. Since distances are symmetric and the distance from an activity to itself is always zero,

the matrix is symmetric with zeros along the diagonal. This method allows for a more flexible sequence comparison by incorporating the nature of activities and their varying degrees of dissimilarity. The total distance between two sequences is then calculated as the sum of the weighted distances at each position:

$$d(x, y) = \sum_{k=1}^n D_{xy,k}$$

In which n is the length of sequences x and y , and i and j are the numerical values of the activities in x and y at position k , respectively. **Figure 2.3** shows our defined distance matrix as a heatmap.

Figure 2.3. Distance matrix considered for Activity-Travel pairwise costs of substitution.

The data were structured chronologically, with each entry representing a single activity. These entries were then divided into segments of 5, 10, and 15 minutes, each labeled according to the travel or activity occurring during that period, as illustrated in **Figure 2.4**. If multiple activities were recorded within a segment, the first encountered activity was used. The sequences were defined with a length of $24 \times 60 / t$, where t is the segment length in minutes. To focus on the most informative time frame, only activities recorded between 8 AM and 7 PM were retained. Sequences with more than 15% missing values were excluded from the analysis. Since participants primarily remained at home during the late evening hours, mobility variability was minimal.

Regarding nighttime data, a significant portion was missing, leading to the assumption that participants were at home. As a result, this period was excluded from further analysis. To streamline the clustering process and minimize the impact of rare activities on model parameters, similar activities were grouped into six main categories: Home, Work/Education, Errands, Leisure, Travel, and Other.

Figure 2.4. Activity-Travel sequence encoding.

Finally, Hierarchical clustering (HC) was performed on the mobility pattern sequences with 5, 10, and 15minute segments to group them into clusters of similar daily routines. Ward’s method (Ward, 1963) was used as a linkage function to produce the input matrix for the clustering. The silhouette score was used to measure the quality of clustering. The mean intracluster distance and the mean distance to the other clusters are combined to compute the silhouette coefficient of each cluster. **Figure 2.5** shows the distribution of travels and activities along the sequences of each cluster, for the three HC methods tested in a sample of 5-min sequences from the Copenhagen experiment.

Figure 2.5. Showcase of two clusters when testing in a sample dataset.

By using these topologies we aim to jointly capture features of daily mobility and travel patterns and to test their influence on the eMOTIONAL Cities’ health and wellbeing signals.

2.4 Early Insights

2.4.1 Descriptive statistics

Figure 2.6 and **Figure 2.7** showcase the variability of the collected physiological signals (in this case, simple heart rate for straightforward understanding) within and across individuals. The former figure underscores the need for personalized models for emotion recognition; whereas the latter showcases the potential of naturalistic datasets for a better understanding of how decisions (and their features) may affect emotional states. Indeed, our early statistical results sustain the link between different daily mobility and activity features and emotions. Significant statistical evidence was observed in several dimensions of this relationship, supporting existing laboratory findings: a greater *heart rate variability* (measured as RMSSD – often used as a proxy

of relaxation and recovery process) for *driving* compared to *bus use* (Wilcoxon rank-sum $p < 0.001$); a greater average *EDA recovery time* (an indicator of autonomic regulation and resilience to stress) during *social* than *healthcare-related* activities; a greater overall median *valence* score (i.e., more positive emotion) of individuals aged 50-year-old or more (Mann-Whitney U-test $p < 0.001$); a lower subjective valence (i.e., more negative emotion) of all sampled activities for individuals with moderate or higher ranking of *chronic stress* (as assessed by DASS specific questions, Mann-Whitney U-test $p = 0.002$). These are just some examples of our initial results, which also contributed to the early identification of limitations of our experiment (e.g., in-home activities can be very diverse, and so their associated emotional responses).

Figure 2.6. Heart rate and activity pattern for three different days of the same participant.

Figure 2.7: Average heart rate by activity type for the full sample population.

2.4.2 Activities and emotions

In this section, we summarise the early joint work between the eMOTIONAL Cities team and the researchers from the Univ. of Chile, Bastian Henriquez-Jara and Cristian Angelo Guevara on the development of a hybrid discrete choice model to examine the relationship between activities, contextual features, latent emotions, subjective well-being (SWB) statements, and physiological data.

Building on previous research (Henriquez-Jara et al., 2025), we developed a panel hybrid model (structural + measurement equations model) that uses physiological data as indicators of latent emotions, complementing subjective statements. Based on the circumplex model of emotions, the model estimates latent valence (emotion type) and latent arousal (excitation level), influenced by activity type and duration, demographics, time factors, and trip attributes for transport-related activities through a structural equation.

Figure 2.8 presents a summary of the significant parameters from the estimation applied to the Copenhagen data. Our findings indicate that transport activity, education, trip duration, and basal depression (measured through psychometric questionnaires) reduce arousal compared to being at work. Latent valence decreases with

health-related activities and, in women, is also affected by activity duration and basal depression. Walking positively impacts both valence and arousal while cycling specifically increases arousal. Leisure activities—including entertainment, socializing, holidays, and sports—have the expected positive influence on emotional states. Transfers also show a positive effect relative to being at work. Additionally, habitual car users experience more positive emotions while traveling by car compared to non-habitual users.

These initial findings provide new insights into the impact of daily activities on both subjective and physiological emotional responses. They highlight how naturalistic experiments can deepen our understanding of daily travel behavior and individual experiences. Extensions to this model include the urban features and the sequential aspect of observations not included in these first estimates.

Figure 2.8. Parameter estimates of the structural equations (significant parameters at $p < 0.1$).

2.4.3 Spatial analysis insights from pedestrian journeys

Figure 2.5 provides a comprehensive design overview of the methodology applied in this study, illustrating the sequential structure of the research process.

Figure 2.5: Design overview for the spatial analysis insights from pedestrian journeys.

As not all the results have been processed so far, here we present those referring to a total of 55 participants who were monitored in the NUTS 3 – Grande Lisboa region for two weeks each, from August to October 2024.

GPS data were processed using techniques to refine stop detection and mode classification, with GPS tracking speed and trajectory and accelerometer data identifying movement patterns. A learning mechanism adjusted classifications based on user feedback, and the routes were mapped in ArcGIS Pro to measure distances. The study area was divided into grid cells (hexagons), with 25-meter buffers generated along the routes.

Hexagons intersecting travel buffers were analyzed using OpenStreetMap (OSM) and Mapillary. OSM data, processed via the Overpass API, categorized points of interest (POIs) into classes, while Mapillary retrieved georeferenced images filtered by proximity and processed using semantic segmentation to identify proportions of urban features such as roads, sidewalks, and buildings. This workflow generated aggregated spatial data for environmental characterization based on adaptations from Costa, M., et al. (2024).

POIs from OSM were grouped into Urban Infrastructure, Services, and Nature, and hexagons within route buffers were aggregated, summing POIs for each category to create route-level data. Hexagons were also classified proportionally across Urban

Structures, Vehicles, Nature, and People, with route-level aggregation calculated using the formula:

$$Trip\ ID = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Category_i}{Number\ of\ Cell * 100}$$

Descriptive analyses detailed route characteristics, participants’ sensations, and environmental attributes by groups based on environmental influence. Pearson’s correlation index was applied to explore relationships between environmental features and feelings, identifying connections between urban spaces and human experiences.

A total of 4,355 trips were recorded, including 2,003 walking trips. Participants evaluated the environmental influence on their feelings using a scale ranging from 1 (little) to 4 (very much) and assessed sensations across six dimensions on a scale from 1 to 6. **Table 2.1** summarizes the averages for each sensation dimension, as well as the time and distance associated with each level of environmental influence.

Table 2.1: Average ratings of environmental influence on well-being and travel metrics.

Environment Influence	Unwell - Well	Discontent - Content	Agitated - Calm	Tense - Relaxed	Tired - Awake	Without energy - Full of energy	Distance (Kms)	Time (minutes)
Little	4.96	4.77	4.78	4.61	4.41	4.32	0.81	9.47
Moderately	4.84	4.74	4.56	4.46	4.28	4.24	0.80	8.95
Quit a lot	5.01	4.93	4.67	4.59	4.42	4.41	1.04	11.28
Very Much	4.96	4.92	4.54	4.46	4.67	4.63	1.81	19.88
Total	4.93	4.79	4.67	4.54	4.38	4.32	0.90	10.12

Urban characterization results, presented in **Table 2.2**, provide further insights into the interaction between participants’ experiences and their surrounding environments. Analysis of Mapillary data demonstrates that the influence of nature increases with higher perceived environmental impact, while the presence of urban structures and vehicles decreases. Conversely, data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) indicate that trips with high levels of perceived environmental influence feature more prominent urban structures and services, whereas natural points of interest (POIs) are more prevalent in trips with low perceived influence.

Table 2.2: Urban characterization by environmental influence levels.

Environment Influence	MAPILLARY				OMS		
	Avg. Urban Structures	Avg. Vehicles	Avg. Nature	Avg. People	Avg. POI Urban Structure	Avg. POI Services	Avg. POI Nature
Little	42.6%	7.1%	38.3%	0.6%	387	32	52
Moderately	39.5%	6.9%	42.6%	0.4%	288	22	30
Quit a lot	40.8%	7.3%	39.7%	0.6%	320	34	36
Very much	37.7%	6.0%	43.4%	0.8%	375	37	34
Total	41.0%	7.0%	40.3%	0.5%	339	29	41

Table 2.3 highlights the correlations observed for trips with greater environmental influence, categorized as “Quite a lot” and “Very much.” The findings reveal that natural elements have a positive effect on well-being, as reflected in significant correlations with sensations such as "Awaked" (0.260), "Full of energy" (0.238), "Well" (0.132), and "Content" (0.102). Additionally, natural POIs show a positive correlation (0.147) with participants’ feelings. In contrast, urban structures (-0.194) and the presence of people (-0.156) were associated with increased fatigue and stress, underscoring the restorative benefits of nature compared to the potentially adverse effects of urban and social environments.

Table 3: Pearson correlation index for trips classified as having "quite a lot" or "very much" environmental influence.

	Urban Structures	Vehicles	Nature	People	POI Urban Structure	POI Services	POI Nature
Unwell - Well	-0.062	-0.023	0.132	-0.126	0.056	-0.049	0.026
Discontent - Content	-0.040	-0.003	0.102	-0.113	0.010	-0.035	-0.028
Agitated - Calm	0.033	0.084	0.026	-0.152	0.152	0.036	0.147
Tense - Relaxed	-0.005	0.063	0.084	-0.156	0.088	-0.016	0.072
Tired - Awaked	-0.194	-0.081	0.260	-0.126	0.042	-0.200	0.068
Without energy - Full of energy	-0.127	-0.103	0.238	-0.116	-0.002	-0.194	0.058

These results emphasize the importance of integrating natural elements into urban planning to enhance emotional well-being and reduce stress in urban settings. The findings also highlight the nuanced ways in which different environmental characteristics influence human sensations and well-being during walking trips, offering valuable insights for urban design and public health policies.

This ongoing study has already identified a correlation between well-being and the presence of nature during trips, linking natural elements to positive feelings and trips, while urban environments and crowds tend to diminish these perceptions. By integrating physiological, spatial, and subjective data, the research highlights the potential of wearable technologies and geospatial methods to better understand the relationship between urban spaces and mental health, providing valuable insights into urban planning strategies that foster healthier and more pleasant walking environments.

2.5 Results from the acute stress and decision-making task

2.5.1 Stress and decision-making

To understand how stress impacts decision-making, participants (exclusively in Lisbon) were randomly assigned to either a stress or a control condition when performing the lab-based indoor fMRI experiment (for a comparative analysis of the choice pattern across both conditions).

In the stress condition, the socially evaluated cold pressor test (SECPT) (Schwabe et al., 2008) was administered to the participants. They immersed one hand (right for left-handed; left for right-handed) including the wrist for 3 minutes into ice water, while they were observed by one experimenter and recorded on video by another experimenter. Subjects were further instructed to keep their hand as long as possible in the water. Participants in the control condition were asked to immerse their hands, including the wrist, for 3 minutes into room temperature water, rather than ice water. The SECPT paradigm was chosen to induce stress following research from Schwabe et al. (2008), which showed that the incorporation of social-evaluative elements increased HPA axis responses to the standard cold pressor test (CPT), eliciting blood pressure and cortisol responses comparable to those observed in response to the well-established stressor Trier Social Test (TSST) (Kirschbaum et al., 1993; Maheu et al., 2005; Schwabe et al., 2007) while representing a quick and efficient alternative.

To assess whether the treatments were successful, participants were required to report subjective stress on the visual analog scale (VAS), with the lower and upper bound of the scale representing a range from “no stress” to “the most stressful”. Four salivary cortisol measurements were also taken during the experiment, at arrival, immediately after treatment, mid-fMRI protocol, and at the end of the fMRI protocol. If stress induction was successful, the results should show increased cortisol levels in the stress condition at the 3rd measurement time compared to the control group – considering that cortisol response is slow, and so its peak should occur around 20 min after stress induction (i.e., at the middle of the fMRI protocol). Furthermore, all experiments took

place between 1:00 P.M. and 7:00 P.M. to control for the diurnal rhythm of the stress hormone (cortisol). Physiological signals including ECG (electrocardiography) and electrodermal activity (EDA) were also recorded throughout the whole session – using BIOPAC MP150, with modules ECG100C-MRI and EDA100C-MRI – to give further insights into the effectiveness of the SECPT protocol in acute stress induction.

To validate that the acute stress manipulation was effective, we looked at the evolution of cortisol and VAS across time for both groups (**Figure 2.6**) and performed statistical testing to confirm whether those differences were significant.

Figure 2.6. Plots illustrating the evolution of cortisol (left-plot) and VAS (right-plot) across time for both conditions (i.e., “STRESSOR” YES vs. NO); and individual cortisol results specifically for the stress condition cases (center-plot), depicting responders (increase) vs. non-responders.

Indeed, statistical testing showed a significant effect of the interaction term between STRESSOR*time on cortisol ($F(2.09,89.85)=9.60$, $p<0.001$) which was corroborated by a mixed effects linear regression controlling for age and gender ($\beta=0.694$, $t(129)=4.30$, $p<.001$ at time point 3). It also showed a significant effect of the interaction term between STRESSOR*time on VAS ($F(2,120)=3.29$, $p=0.041$) Together, these findings show that acute stress was effectively induced as validated by both physiological (salivary cortisol) and self-reported measures (VAS). Moreover, statistical testing showed no significant differences between the 2 groups in any sociodemographic features, personality traits, or psychological scales – apart from DASS-21 depression subscale (which we were blind to at the time of randomization).

After the cessation of the SECPT (or control) procedure, and after a short training stage and structural MRI acquisition, participants performed the two-stage reversal learning task described below, while inside the MRI scanner (Daw et al., 2011). To provide some context, reinforcement learning (RL) theory proposes that decision-making arises from two distinct computationally precise and neurobiologically

grounded learning strategies. Hence, choice behavior arises from a combination of two value learning systems that operate in parallel and whose fundamental difference is whether they rely on previous or *habitual* choices or reflect a *goal-directed* approach with knowledge about task contingencies (Otto et al., 2013). Daw et al. (2011) designed a sequential choice task to distinguish between these two types of evaluation: model-based RL (MB-RL) – which is goal-directed (prospective, directly assessing available future possibilities); and model-free RL (MF-RL) – or habitual (retrospective, chaining reward prediction errors backward across a sequence of actions). On each trial of the proposed two-stage Markov task, an initial choice between two options labeled by (semantically irrelevant) Tibetan characters leads probabilistically to either of two, second-stage “states,” represented by different colors, which, in turn, both demanded another two-option choice, each of which associated with a different chance of delivering a reward (Daw et al., 2011). The structure of the task – inspired by Daw et al. (2011) – is illustrated in **Figure 2.7**.

Figure 2.7. Diagram illustrating the state transition structure (on the left-side) and timeline of the task (on the right side). Each first-choice is predominantly associated with one of the second stage states and leads there more commonly (i.e., 70% of the time – illustrated by the different arrow sizes; and in contrast to a rare transition with 30% probability). The second-stage choices may or may not be rewarded. In fact, to incentivize subjects to continue learning throughout the task, the chances of payoff associated with the four second-stage options change slowly and independently, according to Gaussian random walks.

Following a rewarded trial (e.g., right diagram of **Figure 2.7**), adopting an MF-RL strategy would mean selecting the same first-stage option in the following trial (since it led to a reward). On the other hand, an MB-RL approach would consider that, because the reward followed a rare (i.e., only 30% of the cases) state-transition, the more advantageous option in the following trial would be to select the alternative option at the first-stage (the one that should more commonly lead to the brown stage).

Various studies in the literature have shown that acute stress leads to a higher contribution of the MF-RL or the *habitual* system (focused mostly on past rewards) than the MB-RL or the goal-directed system (which takes into account both state-transition type – either common or rare, as well as the obtained reward). If the acute stress induction had been successful in our experiment, similar results should have been found. This was indeed the case (**Figure 2.8**) – subjects in the stress condition more often repeated rewarded options (regardless of the transition type) while subjects in the control condition would not as commonly repeat rewarded options that resulted from rare transitions (and, mirroring that behavior, also tended to repeat unrewarded options that resulted from rare transitions).

Figure 2.8. Stay proportions, averaged across subjects for the stress (left-side) and control (at the center) groups, and for the whole set of participants (right-side), displaying hallmarks of MF-RL strategies in the stress condition and MB-RL strategies in the control group.

Statistical testing also confirmed those differences were significant. Mixed effects logistic regression showed a significant effect of previous reward in the stress condition ($\beta=0.133$, $z=4.38$, $p<0.001$), but not of the interaction between previous reward*transition ($\beta=0.028$, $z=0.94$, $p=0.349$); and a significant effect of previous reward*transition in the control condition ($\beta=-0.131$, $z=-3.87$, $p<0.001$), as hypothesized. This was corroborated by a significant effect of the 3-way interaction term STRESSOR*reward*transition on the whole dataset ($\beta=-0.160$, $z=-3.51$, $p<0.001$). Considering additional terms for chronic stress (a proxy of which can be given by the 10-item Perceived Stress Scale, PSS-10, which we added to the Lisbon Post-Survey protocol) and its interaction with STRESSOR, reward, and transition, model fit was improved when considering the PSS-10 score (not DASS-Stress nor the end of day stress assessments across the 2 weeks).

The interaction term between acute and chronic stress was not statistically significant, unlike the (positive) interaction between this chronic stress proxy and previous reward ($\beta=0.103$, $z=2.82$, $p<0.01$). This suggests that more chronically stressed participants,

both in stress and control groups, show an increased tendency to repeat the same 1st stage option if it was rewarded, regardless of the transition type. Thus, this MF strategy resulting from higher chronic stress is in line with the behavior under acute stress.

Summarizing, we showed that after successful acute stress induction (via the SECPT protocol), participants exhibited different decision-making behaviors compared to those under control conditions. We also showed that the effect of chronic stress in decision-making resembles that of acute stress, leading participants to adopt a model-free strategy that considers the effect of reward, but not the transition type.

2.6 Ongoing and future analyses

Current work is focused on adding two new layers of analysis, including: (1) chronic stress estimation from the physiological signals collected throughout the 2 weeks; and (2) fMRI analysis to explore the neural correlates of decision-making under stress and how those relate with the propensity to modify urban mobility patterns in the real-life, in response to stress.

The development of the deep-seeded clustering model presented in section 3.3.1 is also at its final stages, as we are preparing a submission on this topic, including results on three different, publicly available, validated datasets. The results on the mobility patterns and stress levels' estimation based on the clustering model presented in section 3.3.2, as well as on the relationship between urban spaces and emotional responses for the city of Copenhagen, as introduced in section 3.4.3, are also currently being generated and will be included in the project's final report.

3. Findings from “Experiment 4: Outdoor neuroscience experiments”

Experiment 4 was implemented in the pilot cities of Lansing, London, Copenhagen, and Lisbon (a very similar protocol was implemented across all pilot cities). To exemplify the results obtained (and to avoid a very extensive report), we will present data collected from the case of Lisbon (and the other city cases will be made available through the eMOTIONAL Cities dashboard presented in D6.6; and also in the eMOTIONAL Cities [SDI infrastructure](#)). Trajectories will be characterised in terms of paths’ characteristics, as well as through environmental observations and individual body and brain physiological responses obtained with a wearable backpack kit (**Figure 3.1**).

Figure 3.1. The eMOTIONAL Cities’ walker and the PLUMA backpack. This is a unique prototype built for this project (with NGR and CLIMA partner’s support); environmental data (microclimate acquisition), physiological data (biosignals acquisition,) and the hardware integration system.

The experiment considered data essential to deepen our understanding of the impact of different urban contexts (with various forms and functions) on the human body and brain activity (**Figure 3.2**). Hence, it was necessary to understand the background of the participants, the characteristics of the paths taken, as well as the data collected at the time of the experiment (environmental, physiological, and self-reported by the participants); before; during, and immediately after the experiment.

Figure 3.2. Data design overview for the experiment, with the context (top) and sensor (bottom) types of data collected.

3.1 Experiment protocol synthesis

In all of the project's case-study cities, a protocol structured in two parts was implemented. We will now describe the various steps of the protocol addressing the recruitment of participants and the required preparation before the real-life walking experiment.

PARTICIPANT RECRUITMENT

As a consequence of our dissemination efforts, close to ninety people showed interest in participating. Hence, a first email was sent to those interested briefly describing the experiment and including a questionnaire to check the eligibility for their inclusion.

Once the participant's eligibility was ensured, a second email was sent to schedule the day and time for the experiment and to conduct the required individual baseline characterisation of the participant. These baseline evaluations included the following questionnaires/scales: Behavioral Inhibition and Activation (BIS/BAS); Anxiety, Depression, and Stress (DASS-21); Personality (HEXACO-PI-R); Psychological Well-being (Ryff Scale); Life Satisfaction Scale (SWLS); and Social Media Use/Addiction (Bergen Scale).

Finally, Immediately before the experiment, a third contact with the participant was performed to confirm the availability and to sign the informed consent.

PREPARING THE EXPERIMENT

At least two researchers helped during the experiment. One provided support to the participant (including water, sun protection, or towel, if necessary,) and the other was responsible for setting up the equipment (including calibration of GPS, selection of EEG cap, preparation of electrodes and sensors, as well as the computer software for data acquisition).

A brief explanation of the methodological protocol and logistics of the walk was provided to the participant immediately before the walk (including instructions for the acquisition of EEG resting state – with eyes opened and eyes closed – at the start; for path directions and also to inform about checkpoints – where they had to stop for 1 minute, followed by a 20-seconds walk and a final questionnaire to evaluate emotional state as well as the perceived naturalness and crowding of the walk).

The suggestion provided by the researchers for the walk was the following: *«Imagine that you have to walk for some routine event (e.g., go to work or the bank) but you have time (i.e., you are not in a hurry). You are going to use the time available to take a walk around the city and, trying to take your mind off everything else; you are just going to observe and focus on what the city has to offer.»*

At the end of the data collection, we have also contemplated a brief interview (sound recorded) to understand the participant's opinion of the experience. We have asked short answers to the following questions: a) *Did you know this part of the city? If so, do you go there often or only occasionally?*; b) *What did you think of this experiment?*; c) *What did you think of the path?*; d) *Which emotions or sensations can you highlight from this walk?*

3.2 Lisbon case-study

3.2.1 Path selection, characterisation and experimental procedures

The city of Lisbon was analysed in light of four distinct types of urban health indicators (described in detail in a technical report – as part of WP4 activities – about [Methodological report for mapping hotspots in Lisbon](#)): a) urban physical environment; b) health; c) socioeconomic; and local stakeholders qualitative assessment (see below details). This approach resulted in a set of Lisbon areas that correlate the variables and make it possible to determine the hotspots. The methodology was the same as that used for the pilot city of London (as in [D4.2](#)).

Under the assumption of morphological, functional, and emotional diversity, the paths were previously defined on the hotspots by different territorial and health stakeholders (urban planners, architects, landscapers, doctors, and others) – see the [Technical report of the Neurourbanism workshop](#) section of [D5.3](#).

As a whole, a total of 20 walks of ~1 Km in Lisbon (6 of them covering scenarios for both Experiments 2 and 4) allowed 90 acquisitions of physiological, environmental, and self-reported data by participants using the ‘eMOTIONAL Cities Walker’ equipment (**Figure 3.3**).

Figure 3.3. Information about people interested (volunteers), their eligibility as well as the final gender and age characteristics of the final participants.

Considering the diversity of the paths (morphologically, functionally and emotionally), we established 6 ‘major typologies’ (**Figure 3.4**) based on the density of buildings, the greenery, and the concentration of people.

Figure 3.4. Defined major typologies for the paths: A. built + green + crowded; B. built + green; C. green + crowded; D. green; E. built + crowded; F. built.

The data collection procedures in Lisbon followed a specific range of requirements (to ensure homogeneity of the dataset). They were carried out between April and October 2024, between 9:00 AM and 7:00 PM, and on days without rain (impossible to carry out with the backpack).

Characteristics of the selected paths

Understanding the paths that are part of the ‘eMOTIONAL Cities Walker’ experience means understanding the territory of the city of Lisbon and the variety of characteristics that make it up. Despite the uniqueness of each city, the diversity of Lisbon’s urban contexts can be representative of other national and international urban spaces.

At the end, a total of 20 paths (6 for both Experiments 2 and 4; and 14 complementary) were performed (**Figure 3.5**). The length of each path is presented in **Figure 3.6**, but overall the experiments covered a distance of 22,500 metres. We considered an average speed of 1.21 m/s to 1.34 m/s, according to age group and gender (Schimpl et al., 2011) – which means that each walk was designed to last around 12 to 14 minutes.

Figure 3.5. The various paths (divided into 8 zones by capital letters in red) used for the Lisbon outdoor walking experiments (6 paths were used for both indoor Experiment 2 and outdoor Experiment 4 – in green; and 14 were complementary to address topics raised by local stakeholders – in light blue).

Figure 3.6. The morphology and length of the various paths used for the Lisbon outdoor experiments.

The paths selected for the Lisbon outdoor experiments fell into seven distinct zones and aimed to reflect as many characteristics of urban spaces as possible that could also trigger a wide range of different physiological responses and emotions on the part of the participants.

Many attempts have been made to classify public space according to a range of characteristics (Carmona, 2013); however, to group the results by their typology (from the point of view of the urban form) thirteen types of public space were identified, and structured to either linear or non-linear (Lynch, 1984; Gehl & Gemzøe, 2001). To adapt to the reality of the city of Lisbon, we also had to consider information about various dominant long-range viewpoints of the city (CML, 2021). Hence, in our methodology (applied to each path) we conducted a comprehensive classification of the paths as a function of the public space type (see for example **Figure 3.7**).

Figure 3.7. An example of a public space characterisation (here for the Lapa path; but a similar classification was performed for each path). The detailed characterisation of the path (as on the left) took into consideration a variety of public space typologies (as presented on the right).

Figure 3.8 depicts in detail the typologies of public space for each of the six paths selected for robust data collection and analysis. Note that we have also identified turning points (marked as black dots along the path) indicating a significant change of direction (i.e., when the angle of turn is between 135° and 180°) and consequently scene view (and to note that the fact that there is a change in typology does not mean that there is a turning point); and also the checkpoints (i.e., parts of the path that were used for both experiments 2 and 4). Furthermore, **Figure 3.9** shows the proportion of public space typologies contemplated in all six paths of the outdoor neuroscience experiments.

Figure 3.8. A full characterisation, in terms of public space typology, for all six main paths contemplated in the outdoor neuroscience experiments.

Figure 3.9. Percentage of each type of public space considering the 20 paths.

Environmental measures

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER

ENVIRONMENTAL METRICS

Particulate Matter 2.5

Particles with an aerodynamic diameter smaller than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (10^{-6}). PM 2.5 predominantly originates from gases and combustion processes (Gosling et al., 2014). These fine particles can **penetrate deep into the lungs**, reaching the gas exchange regions and depositing in the alveoli (WHO, 2006).

Universal Thermal Comfort Index (UTCI)

Internationally recognized standard designed to evaluate the combined effects of **air temperature, wind, radiation, and humidity** on the human body. Includes an assessment scale applicable to both cold and hot conditions. UTCI **provides a measure of "stress"**, referring to the physiological effort required to maintain thermal equilibrium (Błażejczyk et al., 2013). As an apparent temperature index, UTCI **captures how the climate "feels" to the human body**, offering an intuitive representation of thermal comfort (Robinson, 2001).

Noise

Unwanted or **harmful sounds** permeate the environment, posing significant physical and mental health risks, particularly in urban environments. Recognized as a **major environmental stressor**, noise pollution has a wide range of impacts like **auditory damage, stress response activation**, sleep disturbances and immune and metabolic effects (Passchier-Vermeer & Passchier, 2000).

To assess the environmental exposure of each walk, we analyzed three key environmental factors: **air pollution, microclimate, and noise** levels. Air pollution was evaluated through measurements of fine particulate matter (PM2.5), which represents airborne particles with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or smaller. The experienced microclimate conditions were assessed using the Universal Thermal Climate Index - UTCI (Fiala et al. 2012), a widely used biometeorological index for thermal comfort that incorporates air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and mean radiant temperature. Finally, noise levels were measured using A-weighted decibels (dB(A)) to account for human auditory sensitivity.

Individual body physiological measures

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER

PHYSIOLOGICAL METRICS

Galvanic Skin Response (GSR)

Can be split into tonic (slowly varying) and phasic (rapid changes) components. The latter comprises **physiological responses to emotional triggers** (or SCRs), which correspond to peaks in the signal. It is a **good indicator of arousal level**, due to external sensory or cognitive stimuli (Critchley *et al.*, 2000), stress and conflict resolution (Smith & Principato, 1982).

Heart Rate (HR)

It is computed as $60/IBI$, where IBI is the time interval (in seconds) between consecutive beats. It characterizes the emotional state of the participants and **reveals whether a specific event induced stress** (Wagner *et al.*, 2005).

To investigate the impact of environmental factors on individual physiological responses, we measured **galvanic skin response (GSR)** and **heart rate (HR)** as indicators of autonomic nervous system activity. GSR reflects changes in skin conductance due to sweat gland activity, providing insight into sympathetic nervous system activation and emotional arousal. Heart rate, recorded in beats per minute (BPM), serves as a measure of cardiovascular response, reflecting both sympathetic and parasympathetic influences. These metrics were selected due to their sensitivity to environmental stressors, such as noise, air pollution, and thermal discomfort. Averaged values across participants for each measure were considered in the analysis.

Brain activity measured with electroencephalogram

The EEG results shown below relate to the band power activity obtained from metrics associated with different cognitive and emotional states. These include frontal alpha asymmetry (FAA), frontal alpha power (FAP), frontal midline theta (FMT), and theta/beta ratio (TBR). These values were obtained for every GPS datum of the walk, which is sampled at 1 Hz.

This was possible by taking all the EEG data from the beginning and end of the walk and taking the power spectral density of a 2-second window with 50% overlap. To properly map EEG data for each walk it was necessary to average normalized values of the time-frequency data. In this way, for each specific path, data from each participant was z-normalized and then the average was taken for each corresponding GPS point across all these participants.

Due to the low SNR associated with mobile EEG data, an additional moving average was performed for every 30 points. Therefore, the results represent averaged values of relative intra-path EEG metrics. As such a high value of FAA for a specific EEG path can be interpreted as a spatial point that on average elicited higher valence compared with the other points of the map. The following subsections contain the EEG metrics divided into alpha metrics (FAA and FAP) and theta metrics (FMT and TBR), which relate mostly to emotional and cognitive states, respectively.

3.3 Outdoor neuroscience experiments: results from each path

Out of the twenty predefined Lisbon paths, we selected six for analysis and presentation. These specific paths were chosen based on the quality of the collected data and the number of acquisitions, ensuring a robust dataset with a higher number of participants. This selection allows for a more reliable exploration of how different urban environmental characteristics influence physiological and neurological responses. The specific characteristics of the paths also allow for a comparative analysis of varying environmental stressors and their effects on human well-being.

In the following sections, we present the collected data for each of the six selected paths, structured according to the different measured variables. We first outline the environmental parameters recorded along each route, followed by the corresponding physiological and neurological responses observed among participants. This approach provides a comprehensive overview of the complex interactions between urban environments and human responses, contributing valuable insights to urban design and public health research.

3.3.1 Path 1 - Belém (Zone A - Belém & S. Jerónimo)

This path is located in one of the areas of Lisbon with the highest density of architectural, historical, and cultural heritage, with several emblematic monuments and the strong presence of the River Tagus (making it one of Lisbon's main tourist areas). It has good urban health indicators (e.g., air quality, access to green spaces, and high standards in terms of socio-economic characteristics). Large open spaces linked to the waterfront and the communication axis at low levels (east-west) or to specific gardens coexist with residential neighbourhoods and their respective narrow streets.

Figure 3.10. Belém path with the trajectory (in red), starting (A) and arriving (B) points, the checkpoints for specific data collection, and the characteristics of the participants.

Figure 3.11. Some examples of participants running the experiments in the Belém Path.

Noise mapping: this path has a high presence of tourists and two main roads, the N6 and Rua de Belém, both with a lot of traffic and circulation, so it presents high noise values, above the 70 dBA value, which is considered a stressor value. The lower values are in the Vasco da Gama garden.

Figure 3.12. Averaged values of **noise levels** (in A-weighted decibel, dBA) experienced by participants during the Belém Path.

Air pollution mapping: in terms of PM2.5 concentrations, most of the routes had instantaneous average values ranging from 5 to 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. However, higher values were observed near the roads, likely due to the increased traffic emissions in these areas. These elevated levels of particulate matter near roadways highlight the impact of vehicular activity on air quality, contrasting with the relatively lower concentrations along the more sheltered sections of the route.

Figure 3.13. Averaged values of **particulate matter 2.5** (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) experienced by participants during the Belém Path.

Microclimate stress mapping: almost the entire path is free of heat stress, which can be explained by the presence of breezes, both from the river and the ocean (since there is still oceanic influence in Belém), but also by the presence of trees in the Vasco da Gama Garden. The change to moderate heat stress could be due to variations in radiation (shade versus no shade). Further away from the river, at the end of the path, the frequency of moderate heat stress increases.

Figure 3.14. Averaged values of **microclimate stress** (in Universal Thermal Climate Index, UTCI) experienced by participants during the Belém Path.

Galvanic skin response mapping: the arousal state as measured by the GSR rises mainly in two moments: near a children’s park (i.e., alertness likely due to the effects of crowding); and next to the Rua de Belém – a crossing area with high density of tourists trying to cross the road and busy traffic (as they have to stop for pedestrian crossing).

Figure 3.15. Averaged values of galvanic skin response (in μS) experienced by participants during the Belém Path.

Heart rate mapping: the heart rate increases near pedestrian crossings of this path, suggesting a physiological response to increased attention and mild stress. This pattern likely reflects the need for heightened awareness and caution when navigating traffic, as pedestrians assess vehicle movement and decide when it is safe to cross. The findings provide insight into how the design of this particular area influences physiological states, emphasizing the impact of traffic-related factors on pedestrian experiences.

Figure 3.16. Averaged values of **heart rate** (in beats per minute) experienced by participants during the Belém Path.

Brain activity mapping: the analysis of EEG data has revealed an increase in FAA at the end of the walk in the park, suggesting greater relaxation and positive emotional engagement in the natural setting. In contrast, FAA decreases near pedestrian crossings and in areas with high people density, indicating heightened alertness and cognitive effort. These findings reflect how environmental factors shape brain activity, with traffic-related challenges and crowded spaces demanding increased attention and decision-making effort, while natural settings promote relaxation. Moreover, we have also observed a decrease in frontal alpha band power near the same pedestrian crossing in a high urban density area, further suggesting increased attention allocation and cognitive load appropriate for these demanding settings. This decline may indicate cognitive overload when navigating traffic and crowds.

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER

RESULTS P1. BELÉM – Alpha band

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER
RESULTS P1. BELÉM – Cognitive Status

Figure 3.17. Averaged EEG values of **frontal alpha asymmetry** (top-left), **alpha band** (top-right), **frontal midline theta band** (bottom-left), and **theta-beta activity** (bottom-right) experienced by participants during the Belém Path.

3.3.2 Path 2 - Lapa (Zone C - Estrela, Prazeres & Lapa)

This path was located in an irregular zone of the city (also a result of the different layers of interventions in the territory), punctuated by critical open spaces and notable architectural elements. It has various green spaces of critical size, has a low number of people diagnosed with mental illness (depression, anxiety, and dementia) and the air quality (possibly because of the topography and winds) is also considered very good.

02. LAPA TAPADA DAS NECESSIDADES) AV. INFANTE SANTO

Figure 3.18. Lapa path with the trajectory (in red), starting (A) and arriving (B) points, the checkpoints for specific data collection, and the characteristics of the participants.

Figure 3.19. Some examples of participants running the experiments in the Lapa Path.

Noise mapping: due to its diversity, the Lapa trail has two noise profiles. The lowest values are found at Tapada das Necessidades – a quiet green space. Then it is in the vicinity of Infante Santo, a major traffic artery, where the noise levels reach levels considered harmful to health, even exceeding 90 dBA.

Figure 3.20. Averaged values of **noise levels** (in A-weighted decibel, dBA) experienced by participants during the Lapa Path.

Microclimate stress mapping: despite showing generally comfortable conditions along most of the route, moderate heat stress is observed near the viewpoint of Largo das Necessidades – likely due to reduced shade and increased sun exposure. In contrast, lower heat stress levels near Infante Santo may be influenced by the presence of a ventilation corridor, which enhances airflow and helps cool the area. These findings highlight how urban design and natural ventilation play a crucial role in shaping pedestrian thermal comfort.

Figure 3.22. Averaged values of **microclimate stress** (in Universal Thermal Climate Index, UTCI) experienced by participants during the Lapa Path.

Galvanic skin response mapping: the heightened alertness response was notably observed near the viewpoint and at pedestrian crossings. These areas, which likely involved more complex decision-making or increased environmental stimuli, corresponded with moments of higher noise and traffic activity, suggesting that participants' autonomic nervous systems were reacting to these changes in their surroundings. The increase in alertness reflects a physiological adaptation to the heightened environmental demands, such as navigating busy or potentially hazardous areas.

Figure 3.23. Averaged values of galvanic skin response (in µS) experienced by participants during the Lapa Path.

Heart rate mapping: data showed several variations in the cardiac response to the participants' walk, with noticeable increases primarily near traffic-related areas or road junctions. These elevated heart rates were likely a result of heightened stress and cognitive demands when navigating busy intersections or walking near heavy traffic. The physiological response reflects the body's natural reaction to environmental stressors, such as the need for increased attention and decision-making in these areas, which can lead to a higher heart rate as the body prepares for potential challenges or hazards.

Figure 3.24. Averaged values of **heart rate** (in beats per minute) experienced by participants during the Lapa Path.

Brain activity mapping: the data revealed the least variability in the alpha band and frontal midline theta indicating a relatively stable cognitive/emotional state. The maintenance of mental engagement or cognitive demand was likely due to predictable or less demanding sections of the urban scenery. On the other hand, a low theta-beta ratio near or at road crossings indicates a shift in brain activity associated with increased cognitive demand. The theta-beta ratio is often used as an indicator of mental workload and alertness, with lower ratios typically reflecting heightened focus and concentration. The decreased ratio observed supports that participants experienced greater attentional engagement and mental processing when approaching or crossing roads, likely due to the need for increased awareness and decision-making in potentially hazardous or complex traffic environments.

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER

RESULTS P2. LAPA – Alpha band

Very low variability at the second half of the path for alpha power

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER
RESULTS P2. LAPA – Cognitive Status

Again Lapa displays very low variability

Figure 3.25. Averaged EEG values of **frontal alpha asymmetry** (top-left), **alpha band** (top-right), **frontal midline theta band** (bottom-left), and **theta-beta activity** (bottom-right) experienced by participants during the Lapa Path.

3.3.3 Path 3 - Gulbenkian (Zone D - Gulbenkian, S. Sebastião & Avenidas Novas)

This part of the city has been designed as a residential area, but its favourable connectivity with the rest of the town quickly made it a business centre. It attracts a diverse population, both from a socio-economic point of view and in terms of qualifications and age. The mix of residential areas, commercial spaces, offices, and various public facilities allows for this diversity of occupation. It presents high levels of vulnerability to flooding and high temperatures.

03. GULBENKIAN

Figure 3.26. Gulbenkian path with the trajectory (in red), starting (A) and arriving (B) points, the checkpoints for specific data collection, and the characteristics of the participants.

Figure 3.27. Some examples of participants running the experiments in the Gulbenkian Path.

Air pollution mapping: the air pollution during this path remains relatively low. Since PM2.5 is not of biological origin, its instantaneous concentrations are lowest along this path, as the dense tree cover acts as a natural barrier, reducing the dispersion of particulate matter. This highlights the important role of urban green spaces in improving air quality, emphasizing how vegetation can help mitigate pollution and create healthier environments for pedestrians.

Figure 3.29. Averaged values of **particulate matter 2.5** (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) experienced by participants during the Gulbenkian Path.

Galvanic skin response mapping: the level of alertness in participants increased primarily outside the garden along the Gulbenkian's path, with a notable exception at the entrance of an art center located within the garden. These increases in alertness were likely due to the higher concentrations of people in these areas, which may have heightened participants' awareness and caused mild stress. The presence of more individuals likely prompted greater physiological arousal, as the body responded to the social and environmental stimuli, reflecting the participants' increased attention to their surroundings in areas with greater foot traffic and potential social interactions.

Figure 3.31. Averaged values of galvanic skin response (in μS) experienced by participants during the Gulbenkian Path.

Heart rate mapping: a significant increase when participants were outside the garden space was observed, likely due to exposure to higher environmental stressors (such as traffic and noise). As participants re-entered the garden, their heart rates decreased rapidly, from an average of around 100 bpm to 80 bpm. This sharp decline suggests a relaxation response, possibly induced by the calming effect of the green space and reduced environmental stress. The garden likely provided a more peaceful environment, with lower levels of noise and air pollution, promoting a physiological recovery and a return to a state of lower arousal.

Figure 3.32. Averaged values of **heart rate** (in beats per minute) experienced by participants during the [Gulbenkian Path](#).

Brain activity mapping: the analysis of frontal alpha asymmetry (FAA) oscillated frequently throughout the walk. Notably, two regions were highlighted: an initial path of negativity and a final path of positivity, both associated with the action of re-entering the garden. The initial negativity likely reflected a shift in brain activity related to the transition from a more stimulating environment to the calming effects of the garden, while the final positivity suggested a return to a more relaxed state.

The observed frontal midline theta activity observed in the outer areas of the park further suggests increased cognitive attention or emotional processing in this area (possibly due to heightened awareness of their surroundings). Additionally, the theta-beta ratio pattern observed inside the park, suggests a state of heightened mental engagement (possibly due to the positively stimulating environment in this part of the walk).

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER

P03. GULBENKIAN – Alpha band

Prevalent higher alpha indicates a more relaxed state

Figure 3.33. Averaged EEG values of **frontal alpha asymmetry** (top-left), **alpha band** (top-right), **frontal midline theta band** (bottom-left), and **theta-beta activity** (bottom-right) experienced by participants during the Gulbenkian Path.

3.3.4 Path 4 - Baixa (Zone E - Baixa & Graça)

This path includes some of Lisbon's most emblematic and historic areas; traditionally residential and administrative, but currently one of the main tourist areas in the city and the country. The public spaces (traditional shops, numerous convenience stores, handicrafts, restaurants, and cafes) as well as its streets, are essential landmarks in the social life and vibrancy of the city. Despite this, the spatial data analysis on urban health has revealed a high prevalence of problems related to mental and physical health and, at the same time, exposure to poorer air quality and poor accessibility to the nearest green spaces.

Figure 3.34. Baixa path with the trajectory (in red), starting (A) and arriving (B) points, the checkpoints for specific data collection, and the characteristics of the participants.

Figure 3.35. Some examples of participants running the experiments in the Baixa Path.

Noise mapping: the noise levels along this walking path ranged between 70 and 85 dBA, occasionally exceeding these levels on Rua Áurea (and with a noticeable decrease only in Praça do Comércio). These noise levels are typically associated with stress. This pattern is primarily driven by car traffic, and to a lesser extent, the heavy flow of tourists. It is worth noting that the noise levels in Rua do Ouro, a pedestrianized street, are comparable to those on Rua Áurea, at times surpassing 90 dBA, despite the absence of vehicles.

Figure 3.36. Averaged values of noise levels (in A-weighted decibel, dBA) experienced by participants during the Baixa Path.

Air pollution mapping: the instantaneous values of PM2.5 remain relatively low across this path, even if there is some traffic. This could be attributed to the proximity of the river, as blue spaces can help reduce the concentration of particulate matter by promoting mild wind or airflow and dispersing pollutants, resulting in improved air quality in the surrounding area.

Figure 3.37. Averaged values of **particulate matter 2.5** (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) experienced by participants during the Baixa Path.

Microclimate stress mapping: most of the thermal comfort values along this path indicate moderate to strong heat stress, with data collected on particularly hot days, which likely reduced the effectiveness of cooling breezes. Of particular note is the high level of heat stress in Praça do Comércio, which may be attributed to the square's materials and color scheme, as well as the lack of shade, all of which contribute to heat retention and poor thermal comfort in the area.

Figure 3.38. Averaged values of **microclimate stress** (in Universal Thermal Climate Index, UTCI) experienced by participants during the Baixa Path.

Galvanic skin response mapping: the participants' state of alertness was highest near the waterfront, where elevated GSR was recorded. This increased alertness was likely due to a combination of environmental stressors, including the noise from car traffic, the tactile discomfort caused by the cobblestone pavements, and the higher density of people in the area.

Figure 3.39. Averaged values of galvanic skin response (in μS) experienced by participants during the Baixa Path.

Heart rate mapping: an increase in participants' heart rates was found in areas with a high density of pedestrians and near the cars along the river (i.e., due to crowding and the presence of traffic). The presence of cars, noise, and a larger number of people likely contributed to increased autonomic arousal, leading to the observed rise in heart rate.

Figure 3.40. Averaged values of **heart rate** (in beats per minute) experienced by participants during the Baixa Path.

Brain activity mapping: the path showed little variation in alpha band levels overall, suggesting a relatively stable state of relaxed alertness during most of the walk. However, a marked decrease in alpha band activity was observed as participants approached the river, which likely reflects a shift in attentional focus or an increase in cognitive processing related to the change in environment.

The decrease in alpha activity suggests that participants became more mentally engaged or alert as they neared the river, possibly due to the increased sensory stimulation or the need for greater situational awareness. This dip in alpha band activity was followed by another decrease towards the end of the route, possibly indicating a return to a more relaxed state as participants moved further from the river or entered less demanding areas. The findings for frontal midline theta and the theta-beta ratio were closely correlated with the observations in the alpha band, particularly about the allocation of attentional resources.

RESULTS P4. BAIXA – Cognitive Status

Figure 3.41. Averaged EEG values of **frontal alpha asymmetry** (top-left), **alpha band** (top-right), **frontal midline theta band** (bottom-left), and **theta-beta activity** (bottom-right) experienced by participants during the Baixa Path.

3.3.5 Path 5 - Graça (Zone E - Baixa & Graça)

Similarly to the previous path, this one passes through relevant historical and touristic areas. The trajectory is irregular and its public spaces are also socially and culturally very active. The spatial data analysis also has shown a high prevalence of mental and physical health concerns, exposure to lower air quality, and limited accessibility to nearby green spaces.

Figure 3.42. Graça path with the trajectory (in red), starting (A) and arriving (B) points, the checkpoints for specific data collection, and the characteristics of the participants.

Figure 3.43. Some examples of participants running the experiments in the Graça Path.

Noise mapping: most of the paths had noise levels above 70 dBA, which, due to the type of road surface, amplifies the noise from car traffic. These elevated noise levels are typically associated with stress and discomfort. However, noise levels were considered healthy only in Rua do Salvador and Largo do Salvador, where the environment is usually quieter, providing a more peaceful experience for pedestrians.

Figure 3.44. Averaged values of **noise levels** (in A-weighted decibel, dBA) experienced by participants during the Graça Path.

Air pollution mapping: the air pollution values along this path oscillated between 10 and 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. However, higher instantaneous accumulations were observed in Rua das Escolas, which is more affected by traffic. These elevated levels highlight the impact of vehicle emissions on air quality in urban areas, especially in more congested streets.

Figure 3.45. Averaged values of **particulate matter 2.5** (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) experienced by participants during the [Graça Path](#).

Microclimate stress mapping: the path mostly showed moderate to strong heat stress, which could be explained, in addition to the acquisition dates, by the high exposure to direct solar radiation.

Figure 3.46. Averaged values of **microclimate stress** (in Universal Thermal Climate Index, UTCI) experienced by participants during the Graça Path.

Galvanic skin response mapping: the GSR data indicated a heightened state of alertness along the path, which appeared to be linked to intense sensory inputs, such as noise, crowd movement, and potential interactions, which could have prompted an increase in alertness as participants navigated through the busier areas.

Figure 3.47. Averaged values of **galvanic skin response** (in μS) experienced by participants during the Graça Path.

Heart rate mapping: the elevated values during the walk were primarily associated with physical effort, particularly in sections of the path with steep inclines and the presence of stairs. These areas required increased cardiovascular effort to overcome the added physical challenge.

Figure 3.48. Averaged values of **heart rate** (in beats per minute) experienced by participants during the Graça Path.

Brain activity mapping: the analysis revealed a clear division of the Graça route into two distinct segments. The first segment, from the church to the viewpoint, was characterized by low pleasure and higher stress, which can be attributed to the physical effort required for the altitude gain and the presence of a large number of people. These factors likely induced discomfort and heightened emotional reactivity, reflected in the EEG patterns (particularly the activity of alpha band and frontal alpha asymmetry) of increased stress.

In contrast, the second part of the path exhibited a greater prevalence of pleasurable states and regions with reduced emotional activity. This shift suggests that as participants moved through more tranquil or less congested areas, their emotional and cognitive states became more relaxed, leading to a more positive and stable mental response. There is lower variability and sustained cognitive engagement (as reflected by the absence of highlights in the frontal theta band and theta-beta ratio) during most of the path which seems to correlate with the path region of increasing altitude.

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER
RESULTS P5. GRAÇA – Alpha band

A clear inverse correlation suggests high arousal and low valence.

RESULTS P5. GRAÇA – Cognitive Status

Low variability and sustained cognitive engagement during most of the path

Figure 3.49. Averaged EEG values of **frontal alpha asymmetry** (top-left), **alpha band** (top-right), **frontal midline theta band** (bottom-left), and **theta-beta activity** (bottom-right) experienced by participants during the Graça Path.

3.3.6 Path 6 - Parque das Nações (Zone H - Parque das Nações & Oriente)

The area where this path is located is the result of the urban regeneration process that took place in the eastern part of Lisbon following the 1998 World Expo. The data analysed for Parque das Nações shows high purchasing power, a comparatively young population, and low unemployment. There is a good presence and proximity to natural spaces (green areas and waterfront) and the data shows low numbers of people diagnosed with physical illnesses or mental illnesses. Despite the presence of green spaces and waterfront, it is one of the areas of the city with the highest average temperatures and several heat islands.

06. PARQUE DAS NAÇÕES DESCOBERTAS > JARDIM MÁRIO RUIVO

Figure 3.50. Parque das Nações path with the trajectory (in red), starting (A) and arriving (B) points, the checkpoints for specific data collection and the characteristics of the participants.

Figure 3.51. Some examples of participants running the experiments in the Parque das Nações Path.

Noise mapping: in the first half of the path, noise levels were higher, mostly ranging between 70 and 90 dBA. This increase was attributed to two factors: the presence of the hospital at the start and the heavy traffic on Avenida Fernando Pessoa. The second half of the route was quieter, with noise levels varying between 54 and 70 dBA, though the highest values were recorded near the end, due to the waterfall by the entrance to the oceanarium.

Figure 3.52. Averaged values of **noise levels** (in A-weighted decibel, dBA) experienced by participants during the Parque das Nações Path.

Air pollution mapping: air pollution measurements in this path were not particularly noteworthy, with no significant fluctuations throughout most of the path. However, a higher instantaneous concentration was observed near Jardins das Águas, which may be linked to local factors such as traffic or other sources of pollution in that area.

Figure 3.53. Averaged values of **particulate matter 2.5** (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) experienced by participants during the Parque das Nações Path.

Galvanic skin response mapping: the highest levels of attention and physiological arousal were observed at the beginning of the path, particularly near the hospital and where some construction work was happening. These areas likely created heightened environmental stressors, such as loud noises and potential visual distractions, which increased participants' physiological responses.

Figure 3.55. Averaged values of **galvanic skin response** (in μS) experienced by participants during the Parque das Nações Path.

Heart rate mapping: no significant fluctuations or noteworthy changes along the path were noted throughout the walk. This lack of variation could be attributed to the consistent and relatively calm urban environment participants navigated. The absence of physically demanding terrain, high-density crowds, or environmental stressors likely contributed to a steady heart rate, reflecting minimal physical exertion or emotional stress.

Figure 3.56. Averaged values of **heart rate** (in beats per minute) experienced by participants during the [Parque das Nações Path](#).

Brain activity mapping: the data collected along the Parque das Nações route revealed distinct patterns of brain oscillatory activity that corresponded to different mental states. The alpha band and frontal alpha asymmetry data delineated well-defined regions along the path, particularly differentiating the emotional experiences in the river and garden areas. Notably, the segment along the river exhibited heightened levels of brain activity, indicative of a more active, positive emotional state, which was reflected in increased engagement and attention.

Conversely, in the garden area, the EEG data showed a reduction in brain activity, suggesting a shift to a more relaxed and calmer state. These findings imply that while the river section may have stimulated a more dynamic, positive response, the garden area promoted relaxation and lower emotional intensity, likely due to its calming environment and visual stimuli.

Moreover, patterns in the frontal midline theta band and theta-beta ratio, alluded to cognitive engagement notably higher near the river. The neutrality observed in the initial sections of the path further reinforces the idea that the river and garden were key areas influencing emotional and cognitive responses along the route.

EMOTIONAL CITIES WALKER

P06. PARQUE DAS NAÇÕES – Alpha band

Interestingly, the later part of the path shows sustained positive valence but higher arousal near the river, which turns into lower arousal inside the park

Again we see a strong shift in the cognitive state when entering the park

Figure 3.57. Averaged EEG values of **frontal alpha asymmetry** (top-left), **alpha band** (top-right), **frontal midline theta band** (bottom-left), and **theta-beta activity** (bottom-right) experienced by participants during the Parque das Nações Path.

4. Neural effects of naturalness and crowding from outdoor experiments

Beyond the direct physiological and neurophysiological effects of specific urban paths (as presented above), a broader evaluation of urban environments is necessary to understand how brain activity relates to subjective perceptions of city spaces. In this section, we investigate the relationship between electroencephalographic (EEG) responses and two key perceptual dimensions of the urban experience: **naturalness** – the extent to which a space is perceived as green or natural – and **crowding** – the subjective sense of population density and spatial confinement. These perceptual dimensions are crucial, as they influence cognitive and emotional states, potentially modulating stress levels, cognitive load, and overall well-being.

EEG data provide an objective measure of neural activity associated with cognitive and affective processing. By examining EEG responses – and following in relation to perceived naturalness and crowding, we aim to determine whether specific neural patterns emerge in response to more natural or densely populated urban spaces. Importantly, these results are derived from an outdoor experimental setup that closely follows the protocol applied in the controlled laboratory setting of our Experiment 3 – “Understanding the neural processing of urban space through naturalistic stimuli” (see [D5.3](#) for the methodology and results of the respective indoor experiment).

The use of mobile EEG technology enables real-time neural recordings in ecologically valid settings, capturing brain activity as participants navigate real urban spaces. This approach enhances the generalizability of EEG findings by incorporating the complexity of real-world sensory and social interactions that are often absent in traditional laboratory studies.

By bridging controlled experimental methodologies with real-world exposure, our data contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of how urban environments influence neural activity in everyday life. As a whole, we believe the analysis shown below provides insights into how different environmental attributes shape neural dynamics, offering a neurophysiological perspective on urban well-being and cognitive functioning.

EEG data acquisition, processing and analysis for the outdoor data

EEG was acquired using an Enobio 20™ (Neuroelectrics, 2024) with 32 dry electrodes at locations following the 10-20 system. The reference channel was located in the right mastoid (M2), and the GND was placed below it. Signals were collected at a sampling rate of 500 Hz. The data was downsampled to 250Hz and filtered between 0.5 and 40Hz. Then bad channels were automatically rejected and interpolated (*pop_clean_rawdata* method in EEGLAB, 5-second flat channel, 0.8 min correlation with nearby channels, 4 max acceptable high-frequency standard deviation). Then the data was averaged reference, and ICLABEL was applied with the following parameters: brain activity > 0.7, heart > 0.3, muscle > 0.3, eye > 0.3, line noise > 0.3, channel noise > 0.3, and other > 0.3. For the synchronisation with stimuli event, a digital Input event was manually sent during the EEG data recording through NIC2 Software (Neuroelectrics, 2024).

For each participant, we isolated the 10-second segment corresponding to each walking path and divided this data into 4-second epochs with a 2-second shift. This allowed us to analyse the data at different time points throughout the walk. During these epochs, we computed the EmoWave™ features, which included assessments of Working Memory, Arousal, Attention, Valence, Motivation, and Fatigue. These features were used to evaluate induced cognitive and emotional changes. Additionally, we conducted a spectral analysis using Welch's method for the computation of the power spectral density (PSD). This method provided insights into the frequency content of the EEG data. We extracted the average power within specific frequency bands for each electrode, including delta (1-4 Hz), theta (4-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta (13-30 Hz), and gamma (30-40 Hz) bands. This spectral analysis offered valuable information about how different frequency components were affected by the videos.

For the EEG data analysis, we conducted a two-way 2x2 repeated measures ANOVA was conducted for each EmoWave™ feature (valence, arousal, attention, fatigue, motivation, and working memory) considering the factors of Naturalness (Built, Natural) and Crowdedness (Crowded, Not Crowded). We also carried out similar ANOVA tests for the Valence and Arousal responses from the participants in the modified Affective Slider test as well as Pearson's correlations among all the answers.

For the band power analysis we averaged the frequency bands across several electrode clusters. Specifically, we created distinct electrode clusters of interest:

- **Frontal Cluster:** comprising AF3, AF4, Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, F7, F8, and Fz electrodes.
- **Central Cluster:** consisting of FC1, FC2, FC5, FC6, Cz, C3, and C4 electrodes.

- **Temporal Cluster:** encompassing P7, P8, T7, and T8 electrodes.
- **Parietal Cluster:** including CP1, CP2, CP5, CP6, P3, P4, and Pz electrodes.
- **Occipital Cluster:** comprising PO4, PO3, O1, and O2 electrodes.
- **Midline Cluster:** comprising Fz, Cz, and Pz electrodes.
- **Global Cluster:** comprising all the electrodes.

In cases where we identified a significant interaction between Naturalness and Crowdedness, we conducted a subsequent simple main effect analysis for each group. This analysis helped us determine which specific conditions were contributing to the observed interaction effect.

To ensure that our analyses adhered to the assumptions of normality and to address the issue of multiple comparisons, we applied log-normalisation to the power values. Furthermore, we adjusted the p-values for multiple comparisons using the False Discovery Rate (FDR) method (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995). Samples were labeled as outliers and removed from the analysis if their values were 1.5 times greater or lower than the Interquartile Range (IQR).

Forms Analysis: crowdedness and naturalness

Crowdedness form:

- Answer between 7 and 9: *Crowded*
- Answer between 1 and 3: *Not Crowded*
- Answer between 4 and 6: *Neutral*

Naturalness form:

- Answer between 7 and 9: *Natural*
- Answer between 1 and 3: *Not Crowded*
- Answer between 4 and 6: *Neutral*

Forms Analysis: valence and arousal

Lisbon participants answered a Form from 1 to 9 (while Copenhagen participants answered an affective slider form that went from 0 and 1). To maintain consistency, we normalized Lisbon answers between 0 and 1 using the following formula:

$$z_i = \frac{(x_i - \min(x))}{\max(x) - \min(x)}$$

Where z_i is the normalized answer value, x_i is the original value between 1 and 9, $\min(x)$ is 1 and $\max(x)$ is 9.

4.1.1 Results for emotional self-perceived and EEG activity as a function of naturalness and crowding of the outdoor paths

Self-perceived emotional responses

Participants' responses indicated that self-perceived natural paths were associated with higher levels of pleasure (see **Figure 3.58-A**). A positive correlation was observed between self-perceived naturalness and valence ($r = .48, p < .0001$). In contrast, no significant correlation was found between crowdedness and valence. However, self-perceived natural paths were linked to lower levels of arousal, whereas crowded paths were associated with higher levels of arousal. A small but significant negative correlation was found between naturalness and arousal ($r = -.12, p = .02$), and a significant positive correlation was observed between arousal and crowdedness ($r = .33, p < .0001$).

Figure 3.58. Form Analysis **A)** Pearson's correlation between self-perceived Valence and Arousal levels and self-perceived Naturalness and Crowdedness of each path. **B)** Within-participants analysis between Arousal and Valence for each path category (Natural vs Neutral vs Built and Crowded vs Neutral vs Not Crowded)

The within-participants analysis yielded slightly different results. As anticipated, natural paths elicited higher levels of valence and lower levels of arousal. In contrast, crowded paths not only elicited higher levels of arousal but also higher levels of valence (see **Figure 3.58-B**). A repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a significant effect of crowdedness on valence ($F(1) = 32.82, p = .02, \eta^2 = .23$) and arousal ($F(1) = 33.24, p = .02, \eta^2 = .88$). Additionally, there was a significant interaction between naturalness and crowdedness for arousal ($F(1) = 86.04, p = .01, \eta^2 = .19$). Post-hoc paired t-tests for valence showed significant differences between built and natural paths ($T(27) = -5.72, p < .0001$) as well as significant differences between crowded and non-crowded conditions ($T(27) = 2.42, p = .02$). For arousal, post-hoc paired t-tests revealed significant differences between crowded and non-crowded paths ($T(20) = 5.96, p < .0001$). Regarding the interaction effect on self-perceived arousal, significant differences were observed between crowded and non-crowded conditions in natural paths ($T(5) = 2.96, p = .03$) and in-built paths ($T(10) = 6.02, p = .0001$). However, no significant differences were found between built and natural paths under either crowded or non-crowded conditions.

In summary, self-perceived natural paths elicited higher levels of valence and lower levels of arousal in participants. When these results were mapped onto Russell's circumplex model (Russell, 1980), it suggested that participants in natural paths experienced a more serene, relaxed, and calm state compared to those in-built paths (see **Figure 3.59**). These findings align with those observed in the indoor experiment. In contrast, crowded paths elicited higher levels of arousal and tended to elicit higher levels of valence, though this trend did not reach statistical significance in the post-hoc analysis. These findings differ from the indoor experiment, where crowded paths, particularly in natural environments, were associated with lower levels of valence.

Figure 3.59. The results of both Arousal and Valence dimensions are projected in Russell's circumplex plane (Russell, 1980) for each factor (Crowdedness and Naturalness).

EEG responses: EmoWave® feature analysis

Due to an insufficient number of conditions within each participant to conduct a two-way 2x2 repeated-measures ANOVA, paired t-tests were performed to compare crowded versus non-crowded paths and natural versus built paths for each EmoWave® feature.

Results indicated that working memory levels were significantly lower for natural paths compared to built paths ($T(6) = 4.74, p = .003$), with a similar pattern observed for attention ($T(6) = 2.81, p = .03$). Additionally, arousal levels were significantly higher for crowded paths compared to non-crowded paths ($T(9) = 2.69, p = .02$). Paired plots of these comparisons are presented in **Figure 3.60**. These findings align with and are consistent with the results observed in the indoor experiment.

Figure 3.60. EmoWave® features compared across conditions. Significant differences were found at attentional and working memory levels between built and natural paths as well as at arousal levels between crowded and uncrowded paths.

EEG responses: band power analysis

A significant overall reduction in theta power was observed in crowded paths compared to non-crowded paths ($T(10) = 2.5, p = .03$). This effect was particularly pronounced in the frontal ($T(10) = 3.14, p = .01$) and temporal clusters ($T(10) = 2.27, p = .04$). A similar trend was noted between natural and built spaces, with natural spaces exhibiting a general reduction in theta power compared to built paths; however, these differences did not reach statistical significance (see **Figure 3.61**). These findings are consistent with the results observed in the indoor experiment.

Topographic maps at Delta

Topographic maps at Theta

Topographic maps at Alpha

Topographic maps at Beta

Crowdedness - Global - Theta

Naturalness - Global - Theta

Figure 3.61. Band Power Analysis compared across conditions. (Left) Topographies of the percentage of difference (%) in Natural paths compared to Built paths (Natural) and between non-crowded paths compared to crowded paths (non-crowded).

The present findings provide valuable insights into how environmental factors, such as naturalness and crowdedness, influence emotional and cognitive states. Self-perceived natural spaces were associated with higher levels of valence and lower levels of arousal, suggesting a more serene, relaxed, and calm state compared to built environments. This aligns with the indoor experiment findings, supporting the restorative effects of natural spaces. Conversely, crowded spaces elicited higher arousal levels, and while there was a tendency for increased valence, it did not consistently reach statistical significance. These results diverge from the indoor experiment, where crowded conditions were associated with lower valence, particularly in natural spaces.

Cognitive measures further demonstrated that working memory and attention were reduced in natural paths compared to built paths, potentially reflecting the restorative and less demanding nature of natural environments. Crowded paths were associated with higher arousal levels, reinforcing the stimulating effect of social density. Neurophysiological data revealed a significant reduction in theta power in crowded versus non-crowded paths, particularly in frontal and temporal regions, with a similar but non-significant trend observed for natural versus built spaces. These reductions in theta power mirror the indoor experiment findings, suggesting that both crowded and natural conditions modulate neural activity associated with attentional and cognitive processing.

Taken together, the results highlight the complex interplay between environmental attributes and their impact on affective, cognitive, and neural processes. They underscore the importance of context—whether indoor or outdoor—and the potential for natural and less crowded environments to foster more positive and less cognitively demanding experiences.

5. Findings from “Experiment 5: Clinical experiment”

A primary objective of this experiment was to determine whether vulnerable groups and gender-related aspects, especially involving memory deficits and spatial navigation impairments, are significant for urban health design or interventions.

To achieve this, a novel framework was developed using non-immersive virtual reality (VR) technology. The framework enabled the simulation of real interventions in a VR-modeled version of Lisbon and facilitated comparisons with control scenarios. This is a major step in existing literature because current spatial navigation tasks lack the ability to simulate real-world complexity, namely presented in urban environments.

To ensure the robustness of the experimental design, analysis, and interpretation of results, we conducted a comprehensive review of the existing literature on related studies. Following this, we developed a detailed protocol and initiated data collection with both MCI patients and controls, which is still ongoing.

To ensure thorough sample characterization, we performed various neuropsychological assessments and acquired structural brain magnetic resonance imaging on both groups. Currently, we are presenting preliminary analysis and results.

This section is structured as follows:

- 1) description of the experimental protocol
 - the protocol has been published as a preprint in Protocol Exchange and is available online at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2623/v1>;
- 2) behavioural results
 - population demographics;
 - behaviour: comparisons in spatial navigation and emotion-related aspects observed between the control and optimized Lisbon scenarios
- 3) presentation of the EEG results – EmoWave® feature analysis
- 4) presentation of Other ongoing studies for complementary brain and body physiological responses across the VR scenarios

5.1 Experimental protocol

(The following pages of this section present the content of the manuscript published in Protocol Exchange from Nature Portfolio and can also be found online at: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2623/v1>. This work is licensed under a CC BY 4.0 License)

The impact of urban environment on spatial navigation in elderly people with mild cognitive impairment

Pedro Santos-Rocha

`pedro.rocha@medicina.ulisboa.pt`

Mamede de Carvalho Lab, Institute of Molecular Medicine - João Lobo Antunes, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

Ana Bonifácio

Centre of Geographical Studies, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, TERRA Associate Laboratory Portugal; Centre of Geographical Studies, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

André Almeida

NeuroGEARS Ltd., London, UK

Paulo Alcobia

NeuroGEARS Ltd., London, UK;

Andrew Erskine

NeuroGEARS Ltd., London, UK

Marta Conceição

Institute of Physiology, Lisbon School of Medicine, Lisbon, Portugal

João Pedro Marques-Reis

Centre of Geographical Studies, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, TERRA Associate Laboratory Portugal

Tyson Burghardt

Department of Neurology and ophthalmology, Michigan State University, USA

Paulo Morgado

Centre of Geographical Studies, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, TERRA Associate Laboratory Portugal; Centre of Geographical Studies, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

Bruno Miranda

Mamede de Carvalho Lab, Institute of Molecular Medicine - João Lobo Antunes, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal; Institute of Physiology, Lisbon School of Medicine, Lisbon, Portugal

Method Article

Keywords:

Posted Date: April 19th, 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2623/v1>

License: This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

[Read Full License](#)

Abstract

Spatial cognition deficits are particularly prevalent in early stages of Alzheimer's disease and in individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). Previous research using simplistic virtual reality (VR) settings was able to show such navigation impairments. However, the degree to which such results apply to more naturalistic environments remains unknown. Our study aims to test the hypothesis that spatial navigation in an elderly population with MCI could be improved by re-designing an urban space. Twenty-five MCI patients and a similar group of age- and gender-matched controls will be recruited to perform an urban spatial navigation VR task (uSNT). The uSNT is a modified version of the well-known virtual supermarket paradigm (designed to assess both egocentric and allocentric orientation processes), but the VR environment will be a real neighborhood of Lisbon. Specific interventions will be performed to various key parameters (street-level complexity, land-use, design, and green areas) and potential confounding elements (colors, textures, street occupation) of the urban scenario. Furthermore, eye tracking and electroencephalography data will be collected. Details of our task design and methodological approach to compare the navigation performance of both groups will be provided. In the future, we expect that the urban (re-)design interventions will positively impact on the navigation performance of MCI participants, being a clear proof-of-principle, that customize urban planning/design is key to enhance the autonomy and quality of life of such patients. Additionally, this research will establish the feasibility of replicating experimental conditions and ensuring consistency across different studies and subjects.

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) and other forms of dementia pose a significant and growing global health concern, being a leading cause of disability and mortality worldwide (GBD 2019 Dementia Forecasting Collaborators 2022). It has become clear that the pathophysiological onset of dementia may precede cognitive symptoms by several years, which has led to the characterization of mild cognitive impairment (MCI) as an intermediate state between normal aging and dementia (Cheng, Chen, and Chiu 2017; Petersen et al. 1999, 2018). MCI is marked by cognitive deficits in individuals, while their ability to perform instrumental activities of daily living (IADL) remains minimally impaired (Jongsiriyanyong and Limpawattana 2018). Despite a small percentage can remain in the pre dementia stages or even improve their cognitive function, there are no medications approved for MCI to prevent progression to dementia (Sachdev et al. 2013).

Navigation and spatial memory are prone to deterioration with normal aging (Tuena et al. 2021), a phenomenon also observed in the early stages of AD (Puthusserypady et al. 2022). This is due to structural and functional changes in the neural network during aging, also related to the pathology of AD (as well as MCI), and is the major cause of spatial disorientation. This behavioral symptom leads patients to commit navigation errors in community spaces, potentially resulting in them becoming lost in both unfamiliar and familiar environments (Rowe et al. 2011).

From a neuroscience perspective, navigation depends on spatial memory, which involves processes such as encoding, storing, recognizing, and recalling spatial information about the environment, along with the objects and agents within it (O'Keefe and Nadel 1978). Moreover, spatial memory relies on two different reference representations that organize the information coming from the environment: 1) the egocentric representation, which pertains to the individual's location in the environment and is grounded in subject-to-object relations; and 2) the allocentric representation, which pertains to object-to-object relations regardless of the individual's location in the environment (Burgess 2008). Additionally, different neural circuits, governing separate spatial strategies, underlie egocentric and allocentric representations. The former is mediated by parietal lobe and dorsal striatum areas (Chersi and Burgess 2015), while the latter is processed by medial temporal lobe structures (such as the hippocampus and its associations with entorhinal cortex)(Ekstrom AD et al. 2003). In MCI (but also in AD), both egocentric and allocentric navigation strategies are impaired (Plácido et al. 2022; Puthusserypady et al. 2020a).

Recent studies employing navigation tasks in novel environments (Da Costa et al. 2022; David Howett et al. 2019; Puthusserypady et al. 2022) using virtual reality (VR) technology, have shown benefits for early diagnosis of AD and the identification of individuals at higher risk of dementia (Schoberl et al. 2020). Indeed, some authors propose that spatial navigation testing could serve as a sensitive diagnostic marker (Coughlan et al. 2018). Although this type of technology enables the implementation of navigation mechanisms similar to those activated in real-life navigation, current spatial navigation tasks lack in simulating real-world complexity, especially present in urban environments. Recognizing that not only the majority of people now reside in cities (United Nations 2018) but also that specific urban interventions may yield favorable outcomes for individuals with dementia (Marquardt, Bueter, and Motzek 2014), this aspect is particularly important. Indeed, there is a lack of understanding of how external factors (such as outdoor landmarks, road network structure, visibility, etc.) influence navigation in locations where patients feel disoriented (Puthusserypady et al. 2020). This research could highlight potential environmental risk factors for spatial disorientation. Shinazi et al. (Schinazi et al. 2023) studied human navigation performance within a virtual city, however, their primary focus was not on assessing the influence of particular environmental features on spatial navigation.

The present work seeks to establish a novel framework that integrates insights from both neuroscience and urbanism fields to assess the spatial navigation abilities of people with MCI. This was accomplished through the application of non-immersive VR technology used to simulate and modify an actual neighborhood in Lisbon, Portugal. The future goal is to study the impact of different urban environmental features on spatial navigation. These adjustments could serve as a reference for policymakers in making decisions related to urban design.

Reagents

Equipment

Procedure

2. Methods

2.1 Virtual reality system

The urban space was modeled in Blender 4.0 software using 1:1000 cartography as reference, made available by Lisbon City Council, and then imported to Unity Game Engine (version 2020 2.1). A virtual representation of Alfama and Graça neighborhoods, in Lisbon, Portugal, was generated and used as environment for the study of navigation (**Figure 1. a-c**).

2.2 Urban area characterization

One of the future goals is to advise policymakers, suggesting that specific environmental adjustments could offer valuable guidance for their decisions concerning urban design. Therefore, the urban area selected with this purpose in consideration.

The location sits within the historic city of Lisbon, situated between the Tagus River and São Jorge Castle. These neighbourhoods, once primarily residential, have now evolved into tourist destinations, characterized by their unique urban features (either their distinctive social occupations as well as their physical and functional layouts).

From a social perspective, the study area is occupied by an aging resident population, evidenced by a 62% increase in the elderly demographic over the past two decades (supported by the Census 2001, 2011, 2021 PORDATA Estatísticas sobre Portugal e Europa). However, it is also frequented by tourists, typically short-term visitors, and new residents – often young people and foreigners – with lifestyles differing significantly from the existing community. Consequently, it is considered multifunctional due to its diverse uses. In addition to its residential aspects (which are experiencing a gradual decline), the area boasts a collection of significant built heritage (such as churches, convents, streets, and squares that are emblematic of the network of public spaces), and shops and services aimed at catering to the constant flux or urban activity.

Regarding the urban morphology, Lisbon is known for its steeply sloping topography, giving rise to prominent elements like public staircases. While these staircases serve as notable landmarks, they also pose architectural obstacles for individuals with limited mobility. At the same time, the area is rich in viewpoints (formal and informal), offering panoramic vistas and serving as reference points with an open view system.

Urban layout

Concerning the urban layout and design, the area features a main street stretching 100 meters in length and 10 meters in width. This street serves as a vital connection between the upper and lower sections of Rua das Escolas Gerais (**Figure 2. a-c**), accommodating both pedestrian and vehicular traffic, including buses, private vehicles, and streetcars. The urban fabric is characterized by its irregularity, consisting of small built-up blocks surrounded by pedestrian or mixed streets of varying widths. Green spaces and trees are scarce within this environment.

The virtual model created based on this context aimed to preserve the unique attributes of the location, keeping the building volumes intact and accurately replicating the architectural features such as spans and colours. Additionally, efforts were made to retain the elements of the area such as streetcars, stairs, walls, and flooring type. These elements formed the foundation for establishing both control and optimized scenarios.

2.3 Spatial navigation task

The spatial navigation task was adapted from the recognized virtual supermarket test (VST), known for its ability to evaluate both egocentric and allocentric navigation strategies. We chose this test due to its previous use in highlighting navigation impairments in AD patients (Tu et al. 2015). In essence, the task involves presenting different videos of a shopping trolley moving around a virtual supermarket, from a first-person perspective. Each video features the shopping trolley starting from a fixed position and following a different route, whilst making a series of 90-degree turns, to reach a final destination within the supermarket. At the end of each video, participants are queried with sets of questions to test both egocentric and allocentric orientations. However, since our goal is to assess these spatial abilities within environments closely resembling real-world scenarios (namely, cities), and determine whether task performance improves through environmental manipulation, our virtual-reality space contained landmarks (**Figure 3. a**) and features intended to evaluate not only the construction of a mental map but also episodic memory, on the contrary of what happens in the VST. A detailed description of the VST can be found in a previous study (Tu et al. 2015). To reach this goal, we modeled one "control" scenario (see **Table 1**), which is identical to the current real-world conditions, and one "optimized" scenario, integrating dementia-inclusive planning and design guidelines (see **Table 2**). Moreover, we defined simple and more complex trajectories to have a mean of comparison and sensibility in task performance. Similar to the approach used in the VST, we developed a total of 16 videos (**Figure 3. b**), comprising 8 different trajectories replicated in both the control and optimized scenarios (first and second sessions, respectively). Among these, 4 were classified as simple, while the remaining were categorized as complex. Prior to the testing session, participants viewed a practice video trial (20 seconds, 2 turns) to introduce them to the urban environment and ensure that the task instructions were well understood. Additionally, there were two significant modifications: 1) after posing the first and second navigation questions (for each video), an extra question related to emotion ("how did you feel watching this video?")

was included to explore potential correlations between spatial navigation and emotional states (**Figure 3. c-e**); and 2) following each testing session, participants were prompted with a series of scenario-specific questions, covering not only subjective evaluation of navigation ability but also aspects such as sense of belonging, fascination, and spatial coherence (see **Table 3**). The interval between the first and second testing sessions allowed participants to rest briefly and provide their responses. The task paradigm is presented in **Figure 4**.

Complexity

In the VST test, complexity is simply defined by adding a greater number of 90-degree turns (5 turns instead of 3) and time (40 seconds instead of 20), as the layout of the virtual environment was not built to contain distinct spatial representations or notable landmarks. Within an urban environment, even a short linear trajectory can become highly complex if it involves a variety of different and unpredictable elements, such as colors, textures, street activity, as well as factors like lighting conditions, weather, ambient noise, and traffic (Brunec et al. 2023; Marquardt, Bueter, and Motzek 2014b). The brain's mechanisms for processing such diverse information are inherently computationally complex. This led to the requirement for quantifying complex videos, considering urban characteristics. For this matter, variables such as the relativized entropy, connectivity, the isovist, field of view, and the buildings facades complexity were selected. Entropy indicates the degree of space accessibility – a higher entropy value suggests greater difficulty in reaching other areas within the space, and vice versa. Connectivity measures all direct connections that each axial line possesses to other axial lines within its nearby vicinity. Moreover, the isovist represents the area surrounding a point (or centroid) within which an object can freely move in any direction until it encounters an obstacle. In spatial analysis, this area is commonly referred to as a viewshed, and the extent of visibility or movement is measured by the maximum line of sight from the point where the isovist is defined. **Figure 5** represents the visual integration of these metrics within the map of the city, and **Table 4** shows their demography.

We have also computed the Field of View (FOV) analysis in a 3D environment, from to visualize and calculate the amount of space that can be seen from any observer with a specific height from a certain given point in space (**Figure 6**). The process consists of defining a set of check points through the street, to be able to map and calculate the visual field for each checkpoint, and for selecting the facades that fall within that field of view that will afterward be considered for the complexity measurement.

Lastly, the building façade complexity was computed using the box-counting method (Wolfgang E. Lorenz and Matthias Kulcke 2021), which consists of four phases to calculate the fractal dimension of the façades (Francesco Leopardi 2023) within the visual field of the observer, e.g. 1) create a first pre-defined grid and count the boxes that contain parts of the geometry; 2) Overlaying a second grid, where the cell dimensions are half of those in the previous grid, and counting the boxes that contain parts of the configuration; 3) Additional grid systems with cell dimensions always equal to half of the cell in the previous grid, until the minimum box size contains the smallest detail of the object. Then count the

number of boxes for each grid that contain parts of the geometry; 4) create a double logarithmic graph, where the x-axis represents the values $\log(ri)$, where ri can denote the scale factor between the initial grid and the subsequent ones, or the number of boxes arranged along the longer side of the object. Along the y-axis, the values $\log(Ni)$ are represented, where Ni represents the number of filled cells for each grid. The slope of the regression line that approximates the points $[\log(ri); \log(Ni)]$ represents the fractal dimension D_b , that measuring the complexity of the building façades.

Urban scenarios

One first scenario, designated as control, was created to reflect the current urban reality (**Figure 7**). The strengths and weaknesses of the space are documented in **Table 1**. Subsequently, an optimized scenario was devised, taking into account dementia-inclusive planning and design guidelines (Dementia-inclusive planning and design guidelines 2023). All modifications made are present in **Table 2** and are aimed at improving 1) route's visibility and specific visual information: the integration of reference points, and the establishment of specific zones with unique characteristics have been identified as helpful for residents' wayfinding abilities; 2) sense of place: a multi-disciplinary area of research has defined sense of place (SOP) as a combination of beliefs, emotions, and behavioral commitments that result in a sense of specialness for a physical setting – McCunn (McCunn and Gifford 2021) reported that, in community settings, stronger SOP is associated with easier recall and navigation through mental maps, in urban environments; and 3) aesthetics: through the deletion of frequent sights of garbage, graffiti, and disrepair.

Task metrics

Ultimately, the performance in the spatial navigation task was evaluated using five outcome measures. For the first navigation question ("Which way should you turn to face the point where you started?"), the reaction time, and the angular error were collected. Regarding the second question ("Touch the map of the environment to show where you finished"), reaction time was also considered along with absolute distance error on the map, defined as the Euclidean distance between estimated and actual starting point locations. Additionally, two secondary outcomes were included to deconstruct absolute distance errors into their proportional angular and linear components. These measures helped mitigate between-trial variability stemming from the pseudo-random generation of trajectories and starting points, which could influence task difficulty/complexity. A third type of outcome measure involves evaluating the variability in task performance across tasks and over time, both between and within participants. In healthy aging, it is believed that increased within-subject variability in spatial navigation tasks may indicate an increase in neural noise which, in turn, could stem from a disruption in executive control systems and/or dysfunction in neuromodulatory systems (Harris and Wolbers 2012). The intention was to evaluate these statistical outcome measures in patients with MCI. Qualitatively, assessments of spatial coherence, compatibility,

as well as perceptions of fascination, oppressiveness, and navigation ability were considered for each VR scenario (Table 3).

Troubleshooting

Time Taken

Anticipated Results

3. Discussion

The introduction of VR testing has prompted numerous studies to investigate spatial navigation within virtual environments. This is primarily due to the capability of VR environments to be completely controlled and replicated across participants (Bing Liu, Linfang Ding, and Liqiu Meng 2021). Fundamentally, these studies have proven valuable in highlighting how AD pathophysiology gives rise to impairments in cognitive processes involving spatial orientation and navigation, further emphasizing the possibility of such impairments becoming potential markers of the disease. While VR studies focus on the underlying neurocognitive factors of spatial disorientation, in relatively simple environments, there remains a gap in understanding how these factors link to external, urban components, found in the complex environment where these impairments occur. By modeling a VR environment that replicates the present condition of a particular neighborhood in Lisbon, Portugal, our aim was to establish a framework for studying the impact of environmental components (such as visibility and visual information, building complexity, sense of place, and aesthetics) on spatial navigation in a population with MCI. Through the development of the methodology, several aspects warrant discussion. Until recently, most of VR used in research was presented on a desktop display, with movement controlled by a joystick or keyboard (Coutrot et al. 2019). Nowadays, immersive VR, which utilizes headsets and virtual goggles, and in some instances allows for walking, has been employed for navigation testing. This offers the advantage of incorporating body-based cues crucial for navigation. However, these interfaces pose challenges for older people, who are less exposed to technology, and cybersickness remains a significant concern, as such experiences have been shown to induce discomfort in AD patients. Although both immersive and non-immersive VR have advantages and disadvantages, the mentioned negative aspects led us to opt for a non-immersive VR setting. Furthermore, the decision to use video presentations made the task considerably simpler, and thus more engaging and intuitive when compared to immersive setups, while also removing the impact of technology familiarity on task performance.

Moreover, additional potential confounding variables were considered and collected, including age, sex, space familiarity, years of education, as well as surveys assessing stress, attention, sleep, memory, and spatial cognition. These were selected to account not only for cognitive abilities but also for the affective state of the participants, given the cross-sectional design of the experiment.

Regarding the environmental modifications between the control and the optimized scenarios, they were based on dementia-inclusive planning and design guidelines, and with an intention that, in the future, these adjustments could serve as a reference for policymakers in making decisions related to urban design. Even if it is just indirectly, the ultimate goal is to start reducing and mitigating inequalities in urban areas that impact vulnerable groups. Furthermore, this implies that these selections were made not only for their potential positive results but also for their practical applicability in real-life situations. The primary modifications were those that directly affected urban landmarks or reference points. In this context, a landmark represents one item that is stably related to specific locations or directions on the map, playing a crucial role in anchoring the cognitive map to the world. In other words, for a cognitive map to be useful, the organism must possess a mechanism for linking map coordinates to stable elements (landmarks) of the environment that can be identified by perceptual systems. These modifications can influence processes related to egocentric and allocentric navigation strategies, as they may impact the mental calculations of distances between the subject and a landmark as well as between landmarks. Secondary modifications were made to enhance the general perception of cleanliness and safety within the environment. These adjustments (such as “remove the garbage”, “introduce handrails”, “replace steps with escalators”, see Table y) were chosen to explore potential relationships between emotional states and spatial navigation performance. Emotional states were characterized not only by subjective evaluation but also through data collected from the brain (electroencephalography marker of arousal), electrodermal activity (EDA), and heart rate variability (HRV). Some studies suggest that the “affective charge” of spaces is important for wayfinding: environments with strong emotional associations are more memorable, negatively-laden landmarks are associated with improved wayfinding performance and recognition and positively-laden landmarks and high arousing landmarks are linked to enhanced route drawing abilities (Gregorians et al. 2022). Moreover, this might align with research indicating that the presence of safety range may serve as a protective factor against the recurrence of getting lost in AD patients (Kwok et al. 2010). Lastly, to assess potential differences between subjective perceptions of navigation abilities and more objective measures, analyses of EEG time-frequency and structural fMRI data, focusing on brain regions related to egocentric and allocentric navigation strategies, will be carried out. The results will be compared to the survey provided in Table Z (questions related with navigation), for both healthy subjects and patients.

4. Conclusion

The present work aimed at developing an innovative framework for evaluating how environmental factors - such as route visibility and visual information, the sense of place, and urban aesthetics - influence spatial navigation abilities in both healthy subjects and those with mild cognitive impairment. To reach the goal, a virtual reality environment was modeled to simulate real-world settings, and the development of two scenarios featuring distinct urban conditions enabled the testing of the hypothesis. By using neuroimaging techniques like electroencephalography, alongside technologies such as eye tracking and wristbands for monitoring electrodermal activity and heart rate variability, we can obtain robust

physiological data regarding the ongoing processes during each phase of the task. In the future, by showing that urban planning can potentially impact a cognitively impaired population, we intend to provide evidence that could be used to guide practice of urban design for other mental health conditions and ultimately start reducing inequalities in urban areas that affect vulnerable groups, such as those with cognitive disorders.

References

Asgarzadeh, Morteza, Anne Lusk, Takaaki Koga, and Kotaroh Hirate. 2012. "Measuring Oppressiveness of Streetscapes." *Landscape and Urban Planning* 107(1): 1–11. doi:10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.04.001.

Bing Liu, Linfang Ding, and Liqiu Meng. 2021. *Spatial Learning with Extended Reality - A Review of User Studies*.

Brunec, Iva K., Melissa M. Nantais, Jennifer E. Sutton, Russell A. Epstein, and Nora S. Newcombe. 2023. "Exploration Patterns Shape Cognitive Map Learning." *Cognition* 233. doi:10.1016/j.cognition.2022.105360.

Burgess, Neil. 2008. "Spatial Cognition and the Brain." *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1124: 77–97. doi:10.1196/annals.1440.002.

Cheng, Yu Wen, Ta Fu Chen, and Ming Jang Chiu. 2017. "From Mild Cognitive Impairment to Subjective Cognitive Decline: Conceptual and Methodological Evolution." *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment* 13: 491–98. doi:10.2147/NDT.S123428.

Chersi, Fabian, and Neil Burgess. 2015. "The Cognitive Architecture of Spatial Navigation: Hippocampal and Striatal Contributions." *Neuron* 88(1): 64–77. doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2015.09.021.

Da Costa, Raquel Quimas Molina, José Eduardo Pompeu, Emerson Moretto, Juliana Magalhães Silva, Michelle Didone Dos Santos, Ricardo Nitrini, and Sonia Maria Dozzi Brucki. 2022. "Two Immersive Virtual Reality Tasks for the Assessment of Spatial Orientation in Older Adults with and Without Cognitive Impairment: Concurrent Validity, Group Comparison, and Accuracy Results." *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society* 28(5): 460–72. doi:10.1017/S1355617721000655.

Coughlan, Gillian, Jan Laczó, Jakub Hort, Anne Marie Minihane, and Michael Hornberger. 2018. "Spatial Navigation Deficits – Overlooked Cognitive Marker for Preclinical Alzheimer Disease?" *Nature Reviews Neurology* 14(8): 496–506. doi:10.1038/s41582-018-0031-x.

Coutrot, Antoine, Sophie Schmidt, Lena Coutrot, Jessica Pittman, Lynn Hong, Jan M. Wiener, Christoph Hölscher, et al. 2019. "Virtual Navigation Tested on a Mobile App Is Predictive of Real-World Wayfinding Navigation Performance." *PLoS ONE* 14(3). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0213272.

David Howett, Andrea Castegnaro, Katarzyna Krzywicka, Johanna Hagman, Deepti Marchment, Richard Henson, Miguel Rio, et al. 2019. "Differentiation of Mild Cognitive Impairment Using Entorhinal Cortex-Based Test of Virtual Reality Navigation." *Brain* 142(6): 1491–94. doi:10.1093/brain/awz121.

"Dementia-Inclusive Planning and Design Guidelines." 2023. <https://happycities.com/projects/dementia-inclusive-planning-and-design-guidelines> (April 2, 2024).

Ekstrom AD, Kahana MJ, Caplan JB, Fields TA, Isham EA, Newman EL, and Fried I. 2003. "Cellular Networks Underlying Human Spatial Navigation." *Nature* 425(6954): 181–84. doi:10.1038/nature01955.

Francesco Leopardi. 2023. "City and Complexity: The Case of Rua Das Escolas Gerais in Lisbon Assessing the Influence, through the Analysis of Biosignals, of the Effects Generated by the Complexity of the Urban Environment within the Observers's Field of View." doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16229.20969.

GBD 2019 Dementia Forecasting Collaborators. 2022. "Estimation of the Global Prevalence of Dementia in 2019 and Forecasted Prevalence in 2050: An Analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019." *Lancet Public Health*: 105–25.

Gregorians, Lara, Pablo Fernández Velasco, Fiona Zisch, and Hugo J. Spiers. 2022. "Architectural Experience: Clarifying Its Central Components and Their Relation to Core Affect with a Set of First-Person-View Videos." *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 82. doi:10.1016/j.jenvp.2022.101841.

Harris, Mathew A., and Thomas Wolbers. 2012. "Ageing Effects on Path Integration and Landmark Navigation." *Hippocampus* 22(8): 1770–80. doi:10.1002/hipo.22011.

Hartig, Terry, Kalevi Korpela, Gary W. Evans, and Tommy Gärling. 1997. "A Measure of Restorative Quality in Environments." *Scandinavian Housing and Planning Research* 14(4): 175–94. doi:10.1080/02815739708730435.

Jongsiriyanyong, Sukanya, and Panita Limpawattana. 2018. "Mild Cognitive Impairment in Clinical Practice: A Review Article." *American Journal of Alzheimer's Disease and other Dementias* 33(8): 500–507. doi:10.1177/1533317518791401.

Kwok, Timothy C.Y., Kenneth S.L. Yuen, Florence K.Y. Ho, and W. M. Chan. 2010. "Getting Lost in the Community: A Phone Survey on the Community-Dwelling Demented People in Hong Kong." *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry* 25(4): 427–32. doi:10.1002/gps.2361.

Marquardt, Gesine, Kathrin Bueter, and Tom Motzek. 2014a. "Impact of the Design of the Built Environment on People with Dementia: An Evidence-Based Review." *HERD: Health Environments Research & Design Journal*. doi:10.1177/193758671400800111.

Marquardt, Gesine, Kathrin Bueter, and Tom Motzek. 2014b. "Impact of the Design of the Built Environment on People with Dementia: An Evidence-Based Review."

McCunn, Lindsay J., and Robert Gifford. 2021. "Place Imageability, Sense of Place, and Spatial Navigation: A Community Investigation." *Cities* 115. doi:10.1016/j.cities.2021.103245.

Nations, United, Department of Economic, Social Affairs, and Population Division. 2018. *World Urbanization Prospects The 2018 Revision*.

O'Keefe, J., and L Nadel. 1978. "The Hippocampus as a Cognitive Map." *Oxford: Oxford Univ. Press*.

Petersen, Ronald C., Oscar Lopez, Melissa J. Armstrong, Thomas S.D. Getchius, Mary Ganguli, David Gloss, Gary S. Gronseth, et al. 2018. "Practice Guideline Update Summary: Mild Cognitive Impairment Report of Theguideline Development, Dissemination, and Implementation." *Neurology* 90(3): 126–35. doi:10.1212/WNL.0000000000004826.

Petersen, Ronald C, Glenn E Smith, Stephen C Waring, Robert J Ivnik, Eric G Tangalos, and Emre Kokmen. 1999. "Mild Cognitive Impairment Clinical Characterization and Outcome." *Arch Neurol*. doi:10.1001/archneur.56.3.303.

Plácido, Jessica, Creso Alberto Bem de Almeida, José Vinicius Ferreira, Felipe de Oliveira Silva, Renato Sobral Monteiro-Junior, Gro Gujord Tangen, Jerson Laks, and Andrea Camaz Deslandes. 2022. "Spatial Navigation in Older Adults with Mild Cognitive Impairment and Dementia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis." *Experimental Gerontology* 165. doi:10.1016/j.exger.2022.111852.

"PORDATA Estatísticas Sobre Portugal e Europa." <https://www.pordata.pt/portugal>. <https://www.pordata.pt/portugal> (April 10, 2024).

Puthusserypady, Vaisakh, Luke Emrich-Mills, Ellen Lowry, Martyn Patel, and Michael Hornberger. 2020a. "Spatial Disorientation in Alzheimer's Disease: The Missing Path From Virtual Reality to Real World." *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience* 12. doi:10.3389/fnagi.2020.550514.

Puthusserypady, Vaisakh, Luke Emrich-Mills, Ellen Lowry, Martyn Patel, and Michael Hornberger. 2020b. "Spatial Disorientation in Alzheimer's Disease: The Missing Path From Virtual Reality to Real World." *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience* 12. doi:10.3389/fnagi.2020.550514.

Puthusserypady, Vaisakh, Sol Morrissey, Hugo Spiers, Martyn Patel, and Michael Hornberger. 2022. "Predicting Real World Spatial Disorientation in Alzheimer's Disease Patients Using Virtual Reality Navigation Tests." *Scientific Reports* 12(1). doi:10.1038/s41598-022-17634-w.

Rowe, Meredith A., Sydney S. Vandever, Catherine A. Greenblum, Cassandra N. List, Rachael M. Fernandez, Natalie E. Mixson, and Hyo C. Ahn. 2011. "Persons with Dementia Missing in the Community: Is It Wandering or Something Unique?" *BMC Geriatrics* 11. doi:10.1186/1471-2318-11-28.

Sachdev, Perminder S., Darren M. Lipnicki, John Crawford, Simone Reppermund, Nicole A. Kochan, Julian N. Trollor, Wei Wen, et al. 2013. "Factors Predicting Reversion from Mild Cognitive Impairment to Normal Cognitive Functioning: A Population-Based Study." *PLoS ONE* 8(3). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0059649.

Schinazi, Victor R., Dario Meloni, Jascha Grübel, Douglas J. Angus, Oliver Baumann, Raphael P. Weibel, Péter Jeszenszky, Christoph Hölscher, and Tyler Thrash. 2023. "Motivation Moderates Gender Differences in Navigation Performance." *Scientific Reports* 13(1). doi:10.1038/s41598-023-43241-4.

Schoberl, Florian, Cauchy Pradhan, Stephanie Irving, Katharina Buerger, Guoming Xiong, Gunter Kugler, Stefan Kohlbecher, et al. 2020. "Real-Space Navigation Testing Differentiates between Amyloid-Positive and -Negative AMCI." *Neurology* 94(8): E861–73. doi:10.1212/WNL.0000000000008758.

Tu, Sicong, Stephanie Wong, John R. Hodges, Muireann Irish, Olivier Piguet, and Michael Hornberger. 2015. "Lost in Spatial Translation - A Novel Tool to Objectively Assess Spatial Disorientation in Alzheimer's Disease and Frontotemporal Dementia." *Cortex* 67: 83–94. doi:10.1016/j.cortex.2015.03.016.

Tuena, Cosimo, Valentina Mancuso, Chiara Stramba-Badiale, Elisa Pedroli, Marco Stramba-Badiale, Giuseppe Riva, and Claudia Repetto. 2021. "Egocentric and Allocentric Spatial Memory in Mild Cognitive Impairment with Real-World and Virtual Navigation Tasks: A Systematic Review." *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease* 79(1): 95–116. doi:10.3233/JAD-201017.

Wolfgang E. Lorenz, and Matthias Kulcke. 2021. "Multilayered Complexity Analysis in Architectural Design: Two Measurement Methods Evaluating Self-Similarity and Complexity." *Fractal and Fractional* 5(4).

Zhong, Jimmy Y. 2016. "Relating Allocentric and Egocentric Survey-Based Representations to the Self-Reported Use of a Navigation Strategy of Egocentric Spatial Updating." *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 46: 154–75. doi:10.1016/j.jenvp.2016.04.007.

This article is part of the research developed within the eMOTIONAL CITIES Project – *eMOTIONAL Cities, Mapping the cities through the senses of those who make them* – which received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 945307. More information at <https://emotionalcities-h2020.eu>.

Figures

Figure 1

Virtual reality environment of the studied area in the city of Lisbon.

Figure 2

Urban layout of the studied area in the city of Lisbon.

Figure 3

Spatial navigation task.

Figure 4

Task paradigm.

Figure 5

Virtual integration map of the city.

Figure 6

Field of view for the Rua das Escolas Gerais.

Figure 7

Virtual reality of the urban environment.

Supplementary Files

This is a list of supplementary files associated with this preprint. Click to download.

- [Tables.docx](#)

- [FigureLegend.docx](#)

5.2 Behavioural results

5.2.1 Population demographics

Table 4.1 shows the demographic profile of a preliminary pilot population who took part in the Lisbon-based experiment. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences between patient and control groups in terms of age, gender, years of education, or childhood residence (all p-values > 0.05).

The cognitive and psychological evaluations consisted of standardized tests measuring memory (Wechsler memory scale), dementia severity (Blessed dementia rating scale), depression (Geriatric depression rating scale), general cognitive function (Mini-Mental state examination), intelligence (Wechsler adult intelligence scale), subjective memory complaints (Subjective memory complaints scale), comprehensive dementia assessments (BLAD - “Bateria de Lisboa para Avaliação de Demência”) and navigation strategies (Navigational strategy questionnaire). Here in this report, we only present the patient's data.

Table 4.1: Population characteristics that took part in the Lisbon-based experiment.

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS	MCI PATIENTS N=12	CONTROLS N=7
AGE (mean±SD)	76 ± 4.45	74.43 ± 6.78
GENDER		
MEN	6 (50%)	4 (57%)
WOMAN	6 (50%)	3 (43%)
YEARS OF EDUCATION (mean±SD)	6.75 ± 4.47	8.43 ± 5.06
CHILDHOOD RESIDENCE		
URBAN	6 (50%)	4 (57%)
RURAL	6 (50%)	3 (43%)
CLINICAL		
MMSE (mean±SD)	26 ± 2,87	
WMS-III		
VISUAL REPRODUCTION I (mean±SD)	9,78 ± 3,35	
VISUAL REPRODUCTION II (mean±SD)	7,11 ± 2,85	
LOGICAL MEMORY I (mean±SD)	8,22 ± 3,38	
LOGICAL MEMORY II (mean±SD)	7,89 ± 4,88	
WORD LIST I (mean±SD)	8,67 ± 3,35	
WORD LIST II (mean±SD)	9,33 ± 3,61	

WAIS-III		
MATRIX REASONING (mean±SD)	12 ± 3,20	
CODING (mean±SD)	10,33 ± 3,32	
BLESS_{ED} (mean±SD)	5,25 ± 3,92	
GDS (mean±SD)	2,56 ± 2,40	
MMSE (mean±SD)	2,56 ± 2,87	
MCS (mean±SD)	7,33 ± 5,5	
NSQ (mean±SD)		

WMS, Wechsler memory scale; BDRS, Blessed dementia rating scale; GDRS, Geriatric depression rating scale; MMSE, Mini-Mental state examination; WAIS, Wechsler adult intelligence scale; SMCS, Subjective memory complaints scale; BLAD, Bateria de Lisboa para Avaliação de Demência, NSQ, Navigational strategy questionnaire.

5.2.2 Behaviour: comparisons in spatial navigation and emotion-related aspects observed between the control and optimized Lisbon scenarios

We first aimed to determine if the optimized scenario led to improved accuracy in spatial navigation responses after video viewing, **among the MCI patient population**.

5.2.2.1 Egocentric and allocentric navigation errors

As outlined in the protocol, we measured two types of spatial navigation errors (illustrated in **Figure 4.1**):

1) the **egocentric error** was calculated as the angular difference between two lines: one extending from the participant’s chosen position to the screen’s center, and another from the correct position to the screen’s center. This type of process relies on a person’s own perspective and position to orient themselves in space.

2) The **allocentric error** was measured as the Euclidean distance between the participant’s selected click coordinates and the correct coordinates on the map. Allocentric navigation involves understanding spatial relationships between landmarks in a map-like way, regardless of one’s current position or perspective.

Figure 4.1. Demonstration on how egocentric and allocentric errors were calculated. On the left side, there is displayed the image participants saw during the task, regarding the egocentric question, along with an example response and the correct answer. The error was defined as the angle formed between the lines drawn to the center. On the right side, the same is shown but regarding the allocentric question. The error was defined as the Euclidean distance between the click coordinates provided by the participant and the correct answer.

The type of scenario optimization we are implementing shows a trend toward improving allocentric navigation accuracy in patients, though this effect is not yet statistically significant. Moreover, it seems that it does not affect the egocentric navigation strategy (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2. Plots displaying the differences in egocentric and allocentric errors between the optimized (light blue) and control (dark blue) scenarios in the MCI patient population. A trend towards improvement in allocentric performance is observed when the interventions were implemented. N.S stands for statistically non-significant.

This is likely because the main transformations were landmark-focused, featuring enhanced building aesthetics, increased greenery in important decision-points, and improved pedestrian infrastructure (adding rails, removing cars, etc...). While these modifications didn't fundamentally change how people use themselves as reference to navigate, they did influence how they mentally represent and visualize the space, similar to how one would read a topographic map.

Figure 4.3 illustrates an example of allocentric responses provided by the patient number one across all videos, comparing the control and optimized scenarios. On the right side of the figure, representing the optimized scenario, the responses marked in red (“Touch the map of the environment to show where you finished”), provided by the patient, are much more closely aligned with the blue markers, which indicate the correct answers.

Figure 4.3. Example of allocentric responses from patient number one in both a) the control and b) optimized scenarios. On the right side, representing the optimized scenario, the red dots (participant’s responses) are more closely aligned with the blue dots (the correct answers).

Comparing responses to complex versus simpler videos reveals a slight contrasting effect of spatial complexity on navigation strategies. To briefly recapitulate, complexity was defined using urban space metrics, including space network entropy, connectivity, isovist density, and the complexity of buildings facades along each proposed street. This was because we wanted to rely only on this factor to create two levels of difficulty for the task. In **Figure 4.4**, the red rectangles highlight features found in videos classified as complex, while the yellow rectangles indicate features found in videos classified as simple.

Figure 4.4. Differences in urban features between complex and simpler spaces. Red rectangles highlight the studied complexity, which is either graphic-related (illustrated on the left with measures such as entropy, and network connectivity) or visually-related (depicted on the right by the building facades complexity). Yellow rectangles show the characteristics of simpler spaces.

Increased spatial complexity appears to enhance allocentric navigation performance while simultaneously impairing egocentric navigation ability (**Figure 4.5**).

Figure 4.5. Plots displaying the differences in egocentric and allocentric errors between the two levels of space complexity. A trend toward improved allocentric performance and impaired in egocentric performance is observed in more complex spaces (light blue) compared to simpler ones (dark blue). N.S stands for statistically non-significant.

Each of the applied metrics could contribute to this outcome: 1) a higher entropy in the spatial network suggest a more complex – less predictable environment, 2) higher connectivity could enable smoother transitions between different areas, 3) higher

isovist density means that participants can observe more of the surrounding environment at once, increasing their ability to use external landmarks and spatial relationships for navigation, and 4) the diversity and complexity of building facades along streets can provide rich visual cues that support the allocentric navigation.

In summary, these metrics encourage allocentric navigation by providing richer, more detailed spatial cues and relationships that can be used to build a mental map of the environment. This reduces the reliance on egocentric strategies, which, as explained before, focus more on body-centered cues and movement.

5.2.2.2 Valence and arousal

We then aimed to evaluate whether the interventions implemented had an impact on emotion-related aspects. To reach this goal, participants rated two emotional dimensions of their spatial experience.

First, they evaluated the valence (emotional pleasantness) of each video on a nine-point scale, ranging from 1 (very unpleasant) to 9 (very pleasant). This measure assesses how attractive or aversive they found the space. Second, they rated their arousal level—their degree of physiological and psychological activation/alertness—also on a nine-point scale, from 1 (very sleepy) to 9 (very excited). This measure captures how energized or alert the environment made them feel.

The optimized scenario elicited both higher valence (pleasantness) ratings and elevated arousal (alertness) levels among patients (**Figure 4.6**).

Figure 4.6. Plots displaying the differences in valence (on the left) and arousal (on the right) between the optimized (light blue) and control (dark blue) scenarios. The optimized scenario demonstrated higher valence and arousal levels compared to the control scenario. ** indicates a significant level of $p < 0.01$; * indicates $p < 0.05$.

This outcome was anticipated, as the goal was to transform the space into a visually clean, more accessible, comfortable and safe, featuring well-maintained buildings, greenery, seating, and thoughtfully designed urban elements as key considerations.

5.2.2.3 Spatial performance and attentional vulnerability from MCI patients

One third goal, since attention is fundamental to memory function, was to assess the impact of the optimized scenario according to the attentional capacities of patients. In order to evaluate this, we used the attentional related scores from the neuropsychological testing. We were expecting that individuals with MCI and attentional vulnerabilities would perform poorly in the control scenario (more disorganized and confused) compared to the optimized environment (with improved visibility and aesthetics), especially when compared to individuals with MCI without attentional deficits. We were also expecting that MCI patients with attentional vulnerabilities would experience greater benefits from the optimized scenario (although all, regardless of attentional capacity, are expected to benefit from the interventions made).

Figure 4.7 presents two plots comparing the difference between the control and optimized scenarios on both the allocentric and egocentric errors, across different attentional vulnerability states. Positive values indicate improved spatial navigation performance in the optimized environment.

Figure 4.7. Comparison of allocentric (on the left) and egocentric (on the right) errors between control and optimized scenarios across different attentional vulnerability states. Positive values represent improved spatial navigation performance in the optimized environment. N.S stands for statistically non-significant.

People with MCI and attentional deficits appear to exhibit poorer performance (e.g., higher errors rates) in the control scenario and/or are the ones that show the greatest improvements in navigation (both allocentric and egocentric) with the scenario optimization. In allocentric navigation, it is also notable that individuals with superior attentional capacities seem to benefit from the optimized scenario, where those within the normal range of attentional capacities do not appear to experience improvements in this environment. Lastly, as seen before, there is a tendency for the impact of the optimization to be greater in allocentric navigation than in egocentric navigation.

5.2.2.4 Spatial performance related to age and gender

Before comparing the results with the control group of subjects, we aimed to explore the relationship between navigation and emotional aspects, specifically valence and arousal, with both age and gender. A trend is shown suggesting that females tend to perform better with the allocentric navigation strategy, while males excel in with the egocentric (**Figure 4.8**). Although the differences are not yet statistically significant, both males and females show improvement in the optimized scenario, with males displaying notable progress on the allocentric question.

Regarding emotional states, as expected, both genders presented higher valence and arousal scores in the optimized scenario compared to the control. Although some research suggests that males and females can perceive and evaluate spaces differently, the changes implemented were not influenced by gender-specific preferences, indicating that the transformations were beneficial for both. Notably, females showed a significantly higher valence when the optimized interventions were applied (**Figure 4.9**).

Figure 4.8. Comparison of allocentric and egocentric errors between optimized and control scenarios by gender. The bar plots show the mean allocentric error (left panel) and mean egocentric error (right panel) for females and males, separated into optimized (green) and control (light green) scenarios. All differences are marked as 'n.s.' (not significant).

control (light green) scenarios. The numeric values indicate the respective mean errors. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences (n.s) between the optimized and control scenarios for either allocentric or egocentric errors across genders.

Figure 4.9. Comparison of valence and arousal between optimized and control scenarios by gender. The bar plots show the valence (left panel) and arousal (right panel) for females and males, separated into optimized (green) and control (light green) scenarios. The numeric values indicate the respective means. Statistically significant higher valence ($p < 0.05$) was observed only among females in the optimized scenario compared to the control.

The first step we took concerning age was to average the errors patients made in both the optimized and control scenarios and correlate them with age, without considering the modifications applied. Surprisingly, we are observing a different trend: allocentric performance appears to be preserved or even improve with age, while egocentric performance shows a decline (e.g., patients make more errors).

This contradicts the literature, which states that allocentric navigation tends to decline in older adults due to the deterioration of neural structures involved in spatial coding, particularly the medial temporal and related regions. As a result, older individuals are more likely to rely on egocentric navigation strategies in later stages of life. These findings might be influenced by this tendency, and if this population indeed favors egocentric strategies, the results should be normalized accordingly (as it would be normal to exhibit more errors in the egocentric question than in the allocentric). Additionally, the sample size should be increased to better characterize and validate these results in a population with MCI and to perform similar analyses with healthy subjects.

To further investigate how age relates to the optimization, we divided the patients into two groups: those older than the median age and those younger than the median age.

Younger patients appear to show no improvement in either allocentric or egocentric performance, whereas older patients seem to improve in allocentric performance but not in egocentric. This finding introduces new insights to the field, suggesting that the applied interventions are more effective in enhancing outcomes for older MCI populations. However, no differences in spatial navigation abilities are yet observed between younger and older patients.

Figure 4.10. Spearman correlation between age and average spatial error types. The plots display the relationship between age and the allocentric error (left panel) and egocentric error (right panel), regardless of the interventions performed. The blue line indicates the linear regression fit, while the shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval. A negative trend is observed for allocentric errors, suggesting reduced error with increased age, whereas egocentric errors exhibit a slight positive trend.

This contradicts the literature, which states that allocentric navigation tends to decline in older adults due to the deterioration of neural structures involved in spatial coding, particularly the medial temporal and related regions. As a result, older individuals are more likely to rely on egocentric navigation strategies in later stages of life. These findings might be influenced by this tendency, and if this population indeed favors egocentric strategies, the results should be normalized accordingly (as it would be normal to exhibit more errors in the egocentric question than in the allocentric). Additionally, the sample size should be increased to better characterize and validate these results in a population with MCI and to perform similar analyses with healthy subjects.

To further investigate how age relates to the optimization, we divided the patients into two groups: those older than the median age and those younger than the median age.

Younger patients appear to show no improvement in either allocentric or egocentric performance, whereas older patients seem to improve in allocentric performance but not in egocentric. This finding introduces new insights to the field, suggesting that the applied interventions are more effective in enhancing outcomes for older MCI populations. However, no differences in spatial navigation abilities are yet observed between younger and older patients.

Figure 4.11. Comparison of allocentric and egocentric errors between optimized and control scenarios by age. The bar plots show the mean allocentric error (left panel) and mean egocentric error (right panel) for patients younger and older than the median age, separated into optimized (brown) and control (light beige) scenarios. The numeric values indicate the respective mean errors. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences (n.s) between the optimized and control scenarios for either allocentric or egocentric errors across age groups.

Figure 4.12 depicts similar comparisons but for the valence and arousal evaluations.

Figure 4.12. Comparison of valence and arousal between optimized and control scenarios by age. The bar plots show the valence (left panel) and arousal (right panel) for patients younger and older than the median age, separated into optimized (brown) and control (beige) scenarios. The numeric values indicate the respective means. Statistically significant higher valence ($p < 0.05$) was observed only among younger patients in the optimized scenario compared to the control.

While no differences in valence and arousal were observed between younger and older patients, younger patients demonstrated statistically significant higher valence in the optimized scenario compared to the control.

MCI patients versus healthy controls

After evaluating the performance of MCI patients on the task and examining the influence of important demographic variables, we aimed to compare their outcomes with those of age- and gender-matched healthy controls (HC). This comparison is presented in **Table 4.2**. To better visualize these results, Figures 13, 14, and 15 display the corresponding bar plots.

Table 4.2: Comparison of outcomes between MCI patients and healthy controls across both optimized and control scenarios.

OUTCOMES		MCI PATIENTS		CONTROLS	
		N=12		N=7	
SCENARIOS		Optimized	Control	Optimized	Control
ALLOCENTRIC (mean±SD)	ERROR	340 ± 138	387 ± 146	234 ± 123	211 ± 110
EGOCENTRIC (mean±SD)	ERROR	77 ± 22	76 ± 21	68 ± 26	67 ± 22
VALENCE (mean±SD)		6.9 ± 1.1	6.0 ± 1.1	6.6 ± 1.2	5.3 ± 2.1
AROUSAL (mean±SD)		6.6 ± 1.4	6.1 ± 1.2	6.8 ± 1.1	6.1 ± 1.9

Disregarding the modifications made between the control and optimized scenarios, patients exhibited poorer overall performance on the allocentric question compared to HC. Until now, we observe no significant differences on the egocentric scores (**Figure 4.13**).

Figure 4.13. Plots displaying the differences in allocentric (left) and egocentric (right) errors between MCI patients (dark blue) and healthy controls (light blue). MCI patients exhibit significantly worse performance on the allocentric question compared to controls ($p < 0.05$), while no significant difference is observed for the egocentric question.

Figure 4.14 presents the results, highlighting the performance evaluation in light of the developed space optimization.

Figure 4.14. Comparison of allocentric and egocentric errors between optimized and control scenarios in MCI patients and healthy controls. The bar plots show the mean allocentric error (left panel) and mean egocentric error (right panel) for MCI patients and HC, separated into optimized (blue) and control (light blue) scenarios. The numeric values indicate the respective mean errors. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences (n.s.) between the optimized and control scenarios for either allocentric or egocentric errors across MCI and HC.

MCI data, as we previously explored and explained, suggest that the optimization improves the allocentric navigation strategy. The plots show that HC participants did not exhibit differences in their responses to allocentric or egocentric questions in either

the optimized or control scenarios. This lack of difference may be because HC do not experience spatial memory deficits that could benefit from environmental manipulations.

In the virtual supermarket test, which we used as a reference to develop our navigation task, MCI patients perform worse in both egocentric and allocentric orientation compared to controls. However, the VST is designed to minimize the influence of episodic memory, as the spatial layout remains very similar throughout. In contrast, an urban environment could yield different results, as its complexity may engage episodic memory capacities (related with medial temporal lobe structures). While HC tends to perform better overall, this hypothesis warrants further investigation in future analyses.

These brain structures such as the hippocampus and the entorhinal cortex (crucial for allocentric navigation), are often among the first to deteriorate in AD. In fact, recent studies have demonstrated that entorhinal cortex-based virtual reality navigation tasks can differentiate MCI patients at low and high risk of developing dementia. What we are observing could reflect early stages of disease progression. Higher sample sizes are needed to validate these conclusions.

Regarding valence and arousal emotional states, no differences were observed in scores between patients and HC, possibly due to absence of significant differences in brain structures associated with these emotions. Additionally, HC rated the optimized scenario as more pleasant and more stimulating (although not statistically significant).

Figure 4.15. Comparison of valence and arousal between optimized and control scenarios in MCI patients and healthy controls. The bar plots show the valence (left panel) and arousal (right panel) for MCI patients and HC, separated into optimized (blue) and control (light blue) scenarios. The numeric values indicate the respective means. Valence and arousal levels do not differ between MCI and HC, and HC still does not demonstrate significant differences in these values comparing the optimized with control scenarios.

5.3 EEG results – EmoWave® feature analysis

Data acquisition and processing

The EEG data acquisition and preprocessing methods applied here were the same as described for the previous Outdoor Neuroscience experiment. Nonetheless, here for the EEG data analysis of each participant, we isolated the 20-second segment corresponding to each video path and divided this data into 4-second epochs with a 2-second shift. This allowed us to analyse the data at different time points throughout the walk. During these epochs, we computed the EmoWave™ features, which included assessments of Working Memory, Arousal, Attention, Valence, Motivation, and Fatigue. These features were used to evaluate cognitive and emotional changes induced by the videos. Next, we conducted a two-way 2x2 mixed measures ANOVA for each EmoWave™ feature (valence, arousal, attention, fatigue, motivation and working memory) considering Condition (Optimized, Control) as within-subject factor and Group (MCI, HC) as between-subject factor. In cases where we identified a significant interaction between Condition and Group, we conducted a subsequent simple main effect analysis for each group. This analysis helped us determine which specific conditions were contributing to the observed interaction effect. Finally (and as before), to ensure that our analyses adhered to the assumptions of normality (and to address the issue of multiple comparisons, we applied log-normalisation to the power values). Furthermore, we adjusted the p-values for multiple comparisons using the False Discovery Rate (FDR) method (Benjamini & Hochberg, 1995). Samples were labelled as outliers and removed from the analysis if their values were 1.5 times greater or lower than the Interquartile Range (IQR).

EmoWave® Feature analysis

Due to an insufficient number of conditions within each participant to conduct a two-way 2x2 repeated-measures ANOVA, paired t-tests were conducted to compare control versus optimized video paths for each group and each EmoWave® feature. Additionally, independent t-tests were used to compare control versus optimized conditions across groups.

Results revealed significantly higher levels of working memory in HC participants compared to MCI participants ($T(9.8) = 2.48, p = .03$). While MCI participants demonstrated higher working memory levels in optimized conditions compared to control conditions, this difference did not reach statistical significance ($T(8) = -2.05, p = .07$). Similar patterns were observed for arousal, with HC participants showing higher arousal levels than MCI participants, though the difference was not statistically

significant ($T(8.24) = 2.15, p = .06$). Arousal levels significantly increased between control and optimized conditions ($T(7) = -2, p = .03$), and close-to-significant differences were observed for MCI participants between control and optimized conditions ($T(7) = -2, p = .08$). Lastly, attention levels were higher in HC participants compared to MCI participants, approaching significance ($T(3.9) = 2.5, p = .06$). These results are illustrated in **Figure 4.16**.

Figure 4.16. EmoWave® features compared across conditions. Significant and close-to-significance differences were found at attentional and working memory levels between control and optimized video paths as well as at arousal levels.

Band power analysis

A general reduction in power across all frequency bands and scalp regions was observed in MCI participants compared to HC participants (**Figure 4.17**). A significant main effect of Group was found for alpha power ($F(13) = 6.53, p = .02$), with trends approaching significance for beta ($F(13) = 4.23, p = .06$) and gamma ($F(12) = 13.48, p = .003$). At the global level, no significant differences were detected between conditions or for Condition \times Group interactions. However, significant differences between conditions were identified in occipital regions for alpha ($F(12) = 6.21, p = .02$), beta ($F(12) = 4.82, p = .04$), and gamma power ($F(12) = 4.92, p = .04$).

Figure 4.17. Band Power Analysis compared across conditions. Significant increases in optimized conditions were found for Alpha, Beta and Gamma power in occipital areas

The present findings highlight the differential effects of group (HC vs. MCI) and experimental conditions on cognitive and neural dynamics, shedding light on the underlying mechanisms of cognitive impairment and its response to the optimized video paths. A general reduction in power across all frequency bands and scalp regions was observed in MCI participants compared to HC participants, with significant effects of group found for alpha power and trends observed for beta and gamma bands. These reductions are consistent with prior research indicating widespread neural dysregulation in MCI, particularly in frequency bands associated with attentional and cognitive processing (Babiloni et al., 2020; Rossini et al., 2007). While global differences between conditions were not observed, localized effects in occipital regions emerged, with significant differences in alpha, beta, and gamma power.

EmoWave® features derived from EEG recordings revealed higher levels of working memory, attention, and arousal in HC participants compared to MCI participants, with significant or near-significant differences observed across several comparisons. While MCI participants demonstrated trends toward higher working memory levels in optimized conditions compared to control conditions, these differences did not reach statistical significance. Arousal levels, however, showed a significant increase in optimized conditions, particularly for HC participants.

5.4 Other ongoing studies for complementary brain and body physiological responses across the VR scenarios

The following subsections will present examples of analyses currently in progress. For this purpose, patient number one was selected as a representative case. This is a 68-year-old male with mild cognitive impairment.

EEG time-frequency analysis

EEG time-frequency analysis is being applied to explore dynamic changes in brain activity across different frequencies over time, during the visualization of different videos. Comparing the mean EEG power during the visualization of the optimized and control videos reveal noticeable differences (although statistical analyses are required to confirm these findings, across all subjects). These differences are mainly presented in pre-central, parietal and occipital parietal areas, associated with the integration of the sensory information, but also with spatial awareness and navigation (Figure 4.18). However, these analyses are somewhat difficult to generalize due to EEG's spatial limitations. Since it primarily measures electrical activity from the scalp, is it challenging to precisely localize brain activity to specific areas because of the smearing effects of the skull and the signal interference from other brain regions. Event-related potentials type of analysis could be used to link EEG brain data with specific spatial coding features.

Figure 4.18. Mean EEG power comparison between videos in the a) optimized and b) control scenarios. Differences are visible in pre-central, parietal and occipital regions.

Moreover, we also observed differences between complex and simple videos (**Figure 4.19**). This time, the differences were observed in more prefrontal areas, which are linked to executive functions, working memory, attention and focus (and other cognitive processes). This could reflect the potential increased cognitive load required to process more complex environments. However, the same caution should be applied.

Figure 4.19. Mean EEG power comparison between a complex (a) and a simple (b) video. Differences are visible in prefrontal regions.

Furthermore, we still need to determine which frequency bands differ at a specific moment (these results represent the average EEG power during the 40 seconds of video) and relate these differences to 1) the urban spatial characteristics displayed in the video, 2) emotional related aspects, and 3) clinical and demographic features.

Magnetic resonance imaging

T1-weighted MRI images were acquired using magnetic resonance imaging technology. These images are optimized to highlight differences in tissue contrast, where the axon of cells (e.g., white matter) appear bright, and water-rich areas, such as in the cerebrospinal fluid and in the nuclei, appear dark (gray matter). These images allow for the examination of structural differences, such as cortical atrophy associated with aging. This is particularly valuable in clinical settings, as they provide clear visualization of lesions that can be linked to specific symptoms and dysfunctions. Over the past decades, extensive research has focused on identifying the neural correlates of various cognitive functions.

In the context of spatial cognition, the hippocampus and surrounding areas, including the parahippocampal gyrus and entorhinal cortex, located in the medial frontotemporal region, are well-established as critical (Figure 4.20). Studies have shown that individuals with Alzheimer’s disease and MCI exhibit reduced volumes in these regions of interest compared to healthy controls.

Figure 4.20. Brain MRI structural images of patient number one. The hippocampus, crucial for spatial cognition, is highlighted in the red rectangles.

Voxel-based morphometry (VBM) is a neuroimaging analysis technique that allows for the investigation of regional brain anatomy by comparing the local concentration of gray matter between groups. We plan to conduct VBM analysis, which involves normalizing, segmenting, and smoothing the T1 images, followed by voxel-wise t-tests to compare differences in gray matter volume or density between MCI patients and controls. These findings will then be correlated with task outcomes to link hippocampal structural changes with functional impairments. We expect that reduced hippocampal gray matter in MCI patients might be associated with poorer performance on the task. This analysis will be particularly interesting in determining whether spatially complex videos help probe the relationship between hippocampal integrity and spatial memory.

Stress and heart rate variability

Physiological signals offer important insights into the body's emotional reactions and stress levels in response to various stimuli. In this case, these signals were and will be used to compare data across the two scenarios, different levels of space complexity, and during navigational responses. The E4 wearable device enables the recording of blood volume pulse (BVP) data, which can be used to calculate inter-beat intervals, heart rate (HR), and heart rate variability (HRV). It also allows for measurements of skin temperature and electrodermal activity (EDA), from which skin conductance responses can be derived.

Signal values during the visualization of one complex video are compared in **Figure 4.21**, with the optimized scenario shown in black and the control scenario in orange. For example, we can observe the states of emotional relaxation induced by the optimization, which are characterized by lower heart rates. Although indirectly, this type of analysis is appropriate for supporting evidence-based knowledge of the urban interventions developed. In the future, these metrics can also be related to space complexity, adjusting for other demographic variables.

Figure 4.21. Demonstration of data from the E4 wearable device during the visualization of one video in the optimized (lines in black) and control scenarios (lines in orange). The figure displays electrodermal activity, blood volume pulse, temperature, heart rate, and data from the accelerometer.

Introduction of an alternative protocol: Utilizing immersive VR technology with a younger, healthy population

In the previous sections, we explained that we chose a non-immersive VR task for MCI patients to avoid the cybersickness it could cause and the technological complexities associated with it, noting that these external factors would significantly impact task performance.

However, immersive VR enables participants to freely explore the space, allowing active body and head motion during spatial navigation tasks, thereby overcoming the limitations of video paradigms which prevent subjects from integrating proprioceptive and vestibular cues for reorientation and navigation. For this reason, we developed a very similar paradigm using immersive VR, to explore navigation behaviors in an urban environment with younger, healthy subjects (**Figure 4.22**).

Figure 4.22. VR Task paradigm. After a fixation period, participants explore the space for one minute before answering two navigation questions. This process is repeated five times, with different starting locations, in both the control and optimized scenarios.

The scenarios used are exactly the same to those developed for the videos: a control scenario reflecting the reality in Alfama, Lisbon, and an optimized scenario incorporating dementia-inclusive planning and design guidelines. However, in this experiment, participants freely explore the space for one minute before answering the same questions about egocentric and allocentric navigation strategies, using one joystick.

There are five different starting locations (**Figure 4.23**), ensuring participants explore both scenarios five times, covering the entire space. Moreover, participants were instructed to appreciate the space but to avoid lingering too long in any location. The goal is to continue studying how the urban environment influences spatial cognition but to gain greater insight into where participants focus their attention the most.

Figure 4.23. The five different starting locations of the VR task paradigm.

During the task we are collecting data from EEG, an eye tracker, and an empathica device, measuring brain activity, eye movements, and heart rate variability. So far, four participants – three males and one female, aged between 22 and 33 years – have completed the experiment. Considering data from one participant, we can see its mobility patterns across the space (**Figure 4.24**).

Figure 4.24. Participant's mobility patterns across the five starting locations (represented by each color) in the optimized scenario.

For instance, we observe that the participant spent more time in the area marked by the red and green dots compared to the blue and yellow ones. The green area offers a viewpoint overlooking the neighborhood, providing an open space to enjoy the surroundings, while the red zone represents a public square surrounded by characteristic buildings. However, further analyses are needed to determine whether these features influenced performance on the questions posed and to explore how these mobility patterns differ between the control and optimized scenarios.

In conclusion, this document provides preliminary promising insights into how urban environmental interventions impact spatial navigation and emotional responses in individuals with MCI. We were expecting that these interventions would improve performance on the spatial navigation task, as they were designed based on dementia-inclusive guidelines, however, more than provide proof of these principle results, we are also delving deeper into understanding how these interventions influence both allocentric and egocentric processes, particularly focusing on how spatial complexity impacts each. These interventions may foster better spatial representations among MCI patients, potentially compensating for cognitive deficits in spatial processing.

Additionally, we were also expecting higher levels of valence and arousal given the goal of making the space more visually pleasing and accessible. A key aspect that still needs to be assessed is whether the improved navigational performance is due to better emotional states. While emotional improvements were also observed, causality has not been established. This could be explored by integrating both navigational and emotional factors into the same analysis. Moreover, caution should be applied when interpreting these initial results as most of them are still only trends. In the near future, the same analyses will be conducted with larger sample sizes.

Finally, the study also introduces the potential of using immersive VR to further explore the impact of urban design on navigation behaviors in a younger, healthy population, which has the advantage of allowing for a more naturalistic exploration when compared to non-immersive video tasks. This task will provide a closer look at environmental features that participants focus on most to succeed in the task.

At present, MSU has collected data from 4 MCI patients and 1 healthy control, bringing the total population to 24 people. We are expecting that a larger sample size will help validate many of these results and interpretations.

6. Conclusions

Throughout the work developed in tasks T5.6 and T5.6, the outcomes reported in this D5.4 deliverable achieve three of the six objectives of WP5 (the other objectives were achieved by the remaining D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3). First, we have conducted urban outdoor experiments (i.e., both experiment 3 and 4) and collected – with the help of an innovative wearable device, environmental features to relate to emotional-, cognitive- or stress-related body and brain responses (addressing our *Objective 5.4*). Our experiments have considered an age- and gender-balanced design (all outdoor experiments) to capture differences in cognitive and emotional processing (addressing aims defined in *Objective 5.5*). Finally, we also present results from a clinical study (experiment 5) that used VR technology as a tool to help obtain evidence that urban planning and design impacts cognitive function in a vulnerable (addressing key goals of our *Objective 5.5*) and diseased group – such as an elderly population with mild cognitive impairment (addressing our *Objective 5.6*).

As a whole, we have collected various physiological and neurobiological signals reflecting cognitive and emotional processing elicited by relevant urban features in real-life and outdoor environments. The reported results for the three experiments were able to identify relevant brain activity patterns informative on how spaces in cities may shape emotional feelings and decisions. It has also touched upon which urban characteristics humans' value – such as the naturalness and social density of the environment; and ultimately attract us or help us navigate.

More importantly, we believe that these findings also address the more generic expected impacts of the eMOTIONAL Cities project. First, it has generated scientific evidence that can be considered by policymakers as a novel way to improve urban health planning across European cities – for example, by showing that certain urban mobility indicators cause stress-responses that could interfere with our well-being or potentiate (mental) health problems. Secondly, we were able to generate datasets (an urban image stimulus set) that adhere to the “FAIR principle”, aiming to make our research data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. Moreover, we have undertaken innovative work to relate data generated from neuroscience indoor experiments (previously reported in D5.3) with more naturalistic outdoor or real-life settings (and also following internationally recognised geospatial standards). Our experimental efforts have also been shared with partners of the European Urban Health Cluster, allowing others to pave the way for subsequent cross-disciplinary collaborations between geospatial and neuroscience (or biomedical) research.

Finally, above the specific findings reported on each section, we were able to show outputs from a new interdisciplinary approach that has brought together neuroscientists, urban researchers and policymakers to investigate the prerequisites for emotionally and cognitively healthy cities. As an example, social density can be perceived as critical for the vibrancy of neighbourhoods by decision makers and city planners; but at the same time we show that it can impact on the emotions at the individual level. Furthermore, our empirical evidence details how the presence of nature in city walks may lead to psychological benefits (including emotional well-being); and how city design could help the navigation of people with cognitive impairments.

As a whole, we contribute to bridge mixed evidence from spatial (from WP4) and neuroscience (from WP5) to allow cross-referencing and dynamic mapping. For the physical environment, measures such as urban attractiveness, density or greenery were identified and associated with quantifiable physical and mental health metrics (important for WP6). This knowledge will be further explored and could then be used for future policy scenario assessment in different urban settings (and to be showcased in WP7).

7. References

Findings from “Experiment 3: Mobile sensing of stress and emotional effects of daily urban experience”

Bratman, G. N., Anderson, C. B., Berman, M. G., Cochran, B., de Vries, S., Flanders, J., Folke, C., Frumkin, H., Gross, J. J., Hartig, T., Kahn, P. H., Jr, Kuo, M., Lawler, J. J., Levin, P. S., Lindahl, T., Meyer-Lindenberg, A., Mitchell, R., Ouyang, Z., Roe, J., Scarlett, L., ... Daily, G. C. (2019). Nature and mental health: An ecosystem service perspective. *Science advances*, 5(7), eaax0903. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax0903>

Tost, H., Reichert, M., Braun, U. et al. Neural correlates of individual differences in affective benefit of real-life urban green space exposure. *Nat Neurosci* 22, 1389–1393 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41593-019-0451-y>

Berry, B. J. L. (2007). "Chapter 1: Approaches to Urban Policymaking: A Framework". In *International Handbook of Urban Policy*, Volume 1. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing. Retrieved Feb 17, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781847208651.00007>

Castro, S.A., Infurna, F.J., Lemery-Chalfant, K. et al. Are Daily Well-Being and Emotional Reactivity to Stressors Modifiable in Midlife?: Evidence from a Randomized Controlled Trial of an Online Social Intelligence Training Program. *Prev Sci* 24, 841–851 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11212-023-01492-7>

Smets, E., Rios Velazquez, E., Schiavone, G., Chakroun, I., D'Hondt, E., De Raedt, W., Cornelis, J., Janssens, O., Van Hoecke, S., Claes, S., Van Diest, I., & Van Hoof, C. (2018). Large-scale wearable data reveal digital phenotypes for daily-life stress detection. *NPJ digital medicine*, 1, 67. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-018-0074-9>

Wilhelm, P., & Schoebi, D. (2007). Assessing mood in daily life: Structural validity, sensitivity to change, and reliability of a short-scale to measure three basic dimensions of mood. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 23(4), 258–267. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759.23.4.258>

Daw, N. D., Gershman, S. J., Seymour, B., Dayan, P., & Dolan, R. J. (2011). Model-based influences on humans' choices and striatal prediction errors. *Neuron*, 69(6), 1204–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2011.02.027>

Dubois, A., Azevedo, C. L., Haustein, S., & Miranda, B. (2023). Deep-seeded Clustering for Unsupervised Valence-Arousal Emotion Recognition from Physiological Signals. arXiv preprint arXiv:2308.09013. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.09013>

Philip Schmidt, Attila Reiss, Robert Duerichen, Claus Marberger and Kristof Van Laerhoven, "Introducing WESAD, a multimodal dataset for Wearable Stress and Affect Detection", ICMI 2018, Boulder, USA, 2018.

Talha Iqbal, Andrew J. Simpkin, Davood Roshan, Nicola Glynn, John Killilea, Jane Walsh, Gerard Molloy, Sandra Ganly, Hannah Ryman, Eileen Coen, Adnan Elahi, William Wijns, and Atif Shahzad. 2022. "Stress Monitoring Using Wearable Sensors: A Pilot Study and Stress-Predict Dataset", *Sensors* 22, no. 21: 8135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22218135>

Alho, A.; Cheng, C.; Hieu, D.T.; Sakai, T.; Zhao, F.; Ben-Akiva, M.; Cheah, L. Online and In-Person Activity Logging Using a Smartphone-Based Travel, Activity, and Time-Use Survey. *Transp. Res. Interdiscip. Perspect.* 2022, 13, 100524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2021.100524>

Tajaddini A, Rose G, Kockelman KM, Vu HL. Recent progress in activity-based travel demand modeling: rising data and applicability. models and technologies for smart. Sustainable and Safe Transportation Systems; 2020.

Ward Jr., J.H. (1963) Hierarchical Grouping to Optimize an Objective Function. Journal of the American Statistical Association, 58, 236-244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1963.10500845>

Henriquez-Jara, B., Guevara, C. & Jimenez-Molina, A. Identifying instant utility using psychophysiological indicators in a transport experiment with ecological validity. Transportation (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-025-10584-y>

Schwabe, L., Haddad, L., & Schachinger, H. (2008). HPA axis activation by a socially evaluated cold-pressor test. Psychoneuroendocrinology, 33(6), 890–895. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psyneuen.2008.03.001>

Kirschbaum, C., Pirke, K. M., & Hellhammer, D. H. (1993). The 'Trier Social Stress Test'--a tool for investigating psychobiological stress responses in a laboratory setting. Neuropsychobiology, 28(1-2), 76–81. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000119004>

Maheu, F. S., Collicutt, P., Kornik, R., Moszkowski, R., & Lupien, S. J. (2005). The perfect time to be stressed: a differential modulation of human memory by stress applied in the morning or in the afternoon. Progress in neuro-psychopharmacology & biological psychiatry, 29(8), 1281–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnpbp.2005.08.012>

Schwabe, L., Oitzl, M. S., Philippson, C., Richter, S., Bohringer, A., Wippich, W., & Schachinger, H. (2007). Stress modulates the use of spatial versus stimulus-response learning strategies in humans. Learning & memory (Cold Spring Harbor, N.Y.), 14(1), 109–116. <https://doi.org/10.1101/lm.435807>

Otto, A. R., Gershman, S. J., Markman, A. B., & Daw, N. D. (2013). The Curse of Planning: Dissecting Multiple Reinforcement-Learning Systems by Taxing the Central Executive. Psychological Science, 24(5), 751-761. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797612463080>

Findings from “Experiment 4: Outdoor neuroscience experiments”

Câmara Municipal de Lisboa (CML) (2021). Municipal Master Plan Regulation [Regulamento do Plano Diretor Municipal] (approved in 2012 with the 2021 revision). Lisboa.

Câmara Municipal de Lisboa (CML) (2018). Lisbon: Street Design. Public Space Manual [Lisboa: o Desenho da Rua. Manual de espaço público]. Departamento de Espaço Público, Direção Municipal de Urbanismo, CML, Lisboa. ISBN 978-972-8403-46-1

Carmona, M. (2010). Contemporary Public Space, Part Two: Classification. Journal of Urban Design, 15(2), 157–173. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13574801003638111>

Fiala, D., Havenith, G., Bröde, P., Kampmann, B., & Jendritzky, G. (2012). UTCI-Fiala multi-node model of human heat transfer and temperature regulation. International journal of biometeorology, 56, 429-441.

Gehl Institute, S. F. (2016). The Public Life Diversity Toolkit. Version 2.0. Gehl Studio San Francisco.

Gehl, J., & Gemzøe, L. (2001). New city spaces.

Gehl, J., & Svarre, B. (2013). How to study public life. Washington, DC: Island press.

Lynch, K. (1984). Good city form. MIT press.

Roe, J., & McCay, L. (2021). *Restorative cities: Urban design for mental health and wellbeing*. Bloomsbury Publishing.

Russell, J. A., Weiss, A., & Mendelsohn, G. A. (1989). Affect grid: a single-item scale of pleasure and arousal. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 57(3), 493.

Schimpl, M., Moore, C., Lederer, C., Neuhaus, A., et al. (2011). Association between walking speed and age in healthy, free-living individuals using mobile accelerometry – a cross-sectional study. *PloS one*, 6(8), e23299.

Silva, E., Niu, H., Seraphim, A. (2023) Quantitative/Qualitative Mapping Urban health across the pilot studies and for specific sites identified as 'hot spots' during the analysis (Deliverable 4.2 – eMOTIONAL Cities). <https://emotionalcities-h2020.eu/resources/>

Błażejczyk K, Jendritzky G, Bröde P, Fiala D, Havenith G, Epstein Y, Psikuta A, Kampmann B (2013) An introduction to the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI). *Geogr Pol* 86:5–10

Gosling, S. N., Bryce, E. K., Dixon, P. G., et al. (2014). A glossary for biometeorology. *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 58(2), 277–308. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-013-0729-9>

Jendritzky G, Dear R, Havenith G (2012) UTCI—Why another thermal index? *Int J Biometeorol* 56:421–428

Passchier-Vermeer, W. & Passchier, W. (2000). Noise Exposure and Public Health. *Environ Health Perspect*, 108, 123-131. <http://ehpnetl.niehs.nih.gov/docs/2000/suppl-1/123-131passchier-vermeer/abstract.html>

Robinson PJ (2001) On the definition of a heat wave. *J Appl Meteorol* 40:762–775.

WHO (2006) Air quality guidelines - global update 2005. World Health Organization, Copenhagen.

Findings from “Experiment 5: Clinical experiment”

Babiloni, C., Del Percio, C., Lizio, R., et al. (2020). Abnormalities of cortical neural synchronization mechanisms in patients with mild cognitive impairment due to Alzheimer's and other neurodegenerative conditions. *Progress in Neurobiology*, 182, 101677.

Benjamini, Y., & Hochberg, Y. (1995). Controlling the False Discovery Rate: A Practical and Powerful Approach to Multiple Testing. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 57(1), 289–300. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1995.tb02031.x>

Rossini, P. M., Del Percio, C., Pasqualetti, P., et al. (2007). Conversion from mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer's disease is associated with a decline in EEG power. *Neurobiology of Aging*, 28(4), 512–524.

(More relevant references are embedded in the protocol manuscript of Experiment 5)